

NATURANCE

Nature for insurance,
insurance for nature

(Grant Agreement 101060464)

**Deliverable 5.4: Compendium of nature-related
insurance products and guidance for insurers
and policymakers**

***WP5 – Impact - exploitation, dissemination,
communication & engagement***

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Executive Summary

This compendium brings together guidance and real-world examples to help understand and act on the growing intersection between nature and insurance. Compiling the outputs of the EU-funded NATURANCE project, alongside external publications from across the insurance, conservation and policy sectors, it provides a single reference point for practitioners at any stage of engagement with nature-related insurance products. The compendium is intended to lower the barrier to entry for insurers developing new products, policymakers designing enabling frameworks, investors seeking to de-risk nature-based projects, and conservation organisations exploring financial tools. It is designed for those encountering this topic for the first time, as well as practitioners looking to move from awareness to implementation.

The compendium showcases the full range of NATURANCE project deliverables, including nine Innovation Labs convened across Europe that brought together insurers, policymakers, local authorities and researchers to co-design practical solutions for specific hazards and contexts, and five supporting research deliverables addressing interconnected challenges such as equitable business models, policy reforms and improved methods for quantifying nature-based solution performance. These are complemented by external guidance from organisations including the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) and The Geneva Association, which together provide strategic framing, evidence tools and implementation guidance. [Annex A](#) contains a summary of cross-cutting themes and recommendations identified from the guidance. Key observations include:

- Nature-related risks are often subject to modelling gaps. Catastrophe models often do not yet include natural assets as parameters, limiting the ability to estimate risk-reduction benefits from nature;
- The available products are primarily risk transfer mechanisms, with integrated risk reduction elements not yet fully mainstreamed. Enablers of risk reduction include underwriting incentives, parametric triggers for ecosystem repair, and community co-design approaches;
- Projects integrating nature-based solutions (NbS) often lack reliable revenue streams, which can make it difficult to fund premiums for nature-related insurance products; and
- Contract cycles may be misaligned with ecosystem recovery timescales. Potential solutions include rolling renewals, performance monitoring, and addressing landowner liability concerns.

The compendium also provides an evidence base of 21 nature-related insurance products, drawing on a [digital library](#) of 47 case studies available on the NATURANCE website. These range from

parametric coral reef insurance and community-based flood schemes to carbon credit delivery coverage and premium discounts for nature-based risk reduction. To enhance usability, case studies are organised by type of insurance, the outcome of the insurance, trigger mechanism and insurance target, amongst other fields. [Annex B](#) contains the full typology of fields, including definitions, and [Annex C](#) introduces a risk-based framework that has been used to categorise case studies, aligned with the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosure (TNFD)'s definitions of nature-related risks. Key observations include:

- Nature-related insurance product launches have grown year-on-year, accelerating since 2019. 81% of nature-related insurance products in the digital library are active, indicating sufficient viability to sustain operations, while 19% are still in the concept or design stage.
- Emerging markets are well represented in the digital library, particularly Asia-Pacific and Latin America and the Caribbean which hold 46% of total case studies. Conversely, Sub-Saharan Africa accounts for only 6% of case studies.
- Indemnity-based triggers remain most common, covering 64% of cases. For parametric schemes 75% were established in the past three years reflecting their novelty, with the majority based in the Global South.
- 74% of products identified were designed to address risks to nature, e.g. ecosystem degradation or species extinction risk. Schemes designed to address nature-related transition risk (e.g. liability insurance for integrating nature into risk management plans) accounted for only 6% of case studies, suggesting this is an opportunity for future development.
- When mapped to the sustainable development goals (SDGs), products were found to primarily align with Climate Action (SDG 13: 81%), Life on Land (SDG 15: 62%), Partnerships for the Goals (SDG 17: 57%) and Life Below Water (SDG 14: 51%).
- Explicit risk reduction elements feature in less than a third of products. Greater integration with risk transfer represents an opportunity to strengthen effectiveness and viability.

Analysis of the NATURANCE findings and the wider literature finds that a consistent picture emerges: insurance can play a far more expansive role in climate adaptation and nature protection than traditional post-disaster compensation. However, realising this potential requires collaboration across sectors, product designs that combine risk transfer with risk reduction, improved data and methods to quantify nature-related risks and risk reduction benefits, and attention to how costs and benefits are distributed.

We gratefully acknowledge the organisations and individuals that shared case studies for inclusion to this report, including UNEP FI and the Ocean Risk and Resilience Action Alliance (ORRAA). Note that sharing case studies does not imply that the organisation is involved in the creation or operation of that product.

1. Introduction

Nature underpins economies, livelihoods and communities, providing ecosystem services that range from food production and water security to flood regulation and carbon sequestration. As the forests, wetlands and reefs that act as natural defences are degraded, and climate-related losses mount, a growing body of work is now exploring how insurance can respond, not only by compensating for losses but by protecting and restoring the natural assets that provide resilience. Yet for practitioners seeking to act on this agenda, whether designing insurance solutions, shaping regulation, or directing investment, the landscape of available guidance and real-world examples remains fragmented across organisations, frameworks and publications.

Developed as a core output of the NATURANCE project, the compendium addresses this gap by bringing together and analysing the guidance and case studies that define the current state of play at the intersection of nature and insurance, including showcasing NATURANCE outputs and demonstrating how they fit within the wider landscape of resources. It is designed to be a practical reference for insurers, policymakers, researchers, investors, conservation organisations and others working to understand what has been done, what works, and where the opportunities lie.

1.1 What is the NATURANCE project?

NATURANCE is a Horizon Europe-funded research project examining how the insurance sector can support the uptake of nature-based solutions for climate adaptation, exploring opportunities across both underwriting and investment activities. Through a series of nine Innovation Labs convened across Europe, the project has brought together insurers, reinsurers, policymakers, local authorities, landowners and researchers to co-design practical solutions tailored to specific hazards and contexts, from flood resilience in the Netherlands and wildfire risk in the Mediterranean to wetland restoration in Sweden and urban heat in London. This stakeholder-driven approach has proven to be an innovation in itself, generating insights that would not have emerged from siloed research or consultation. The project's deliverables address interconnected challenges: how risk transfer mechanisms can complement and incentivise risk reduction through nature-based solutions; how equity considerations should be embedded into scheme designs; how improved methods can better quantify the risk-reduction potential and co-benefits of nature for insurance pricing; and what policy and governance reforms are needed to mainstream these approaches.

1.2 Document User Guide

This compendium is organised in three parts to help readers navigate the resources ranging from guidance to practice.

Section 2 presents a collection of guidance and literature, drawing first on the outputs of the NATURANCE project itself (**Section 2.1**), including the nine Innovation Labs and supporting deliverables, as well as external publications (**Section 2.2**) that extend and complement those findings. Each resource is tagged by target audience, knowledge level and regional coverage. **Section 2.3** provides a summary of cross-cutting findings and recommendations from the guidance.

Section 3 presents a collection of real-world case studies illustrating how insurance is being applied to address nature-related risks, including case studies identified throughout the course of the NATURANCE project. Cases are organised by three categories defined by the UNEP FI Insurance Framework: Insurance for Nature Positive, Resilience Insurance, and Transition Insurance. They range from early-stage concepts to established programmes operating at scale, offering a realistic picture of where the field stands and where innovation is still needed. The cases outlined in this document represent a curated subset of a broader **digital library** of 47 cases, which is available on the NATURANCE website.

Section 4 brings together key takeaways for policymakers, designers of insurance solutions and financial institutions, drawing on the **digital library** of case studies, including assessment of which product designs are gaining traction, where gaps remain, and how insurance can be designed to combine risk transfer with risk reduction in ways that are both effective and equitable.

Annex A provides a summary of cross-cutting themes and findings from the guidance and literature identified in Section 2, including NATURANCE outputs.

Annex B provides definitions for all fields and field values used throughout, organised into two sections corresponding to Literature and Guidance, and Case Studies.

Annex C introduces a risk-based framework for understanding the risks addressed by nature-based insurance products, aligned with the TNFD definitions of nature-related risks and used as one of the defining categories for assessing the case studies in Section 3.

The compendium is intended to lower the barrier to entry for those seeking to engage with nature-based insurance, whether new to the topic or looking to move from awareness to implementation.

1.3 Scope and Methodology

Defining nature-related insurance products. Nature-related insurance products refer to insurance products, in the sense that a premium is paid under an insurance policy, that either benefit or reduce risks to nature (insurance for nature positive), leverage nature to reduce physical risk (resilience insurance), or address risks arising from the transition toward nature-positive practices (transition insurance). Broader risk management services offered by insurers such as risk modelling, risk advisory or stand-alone technical assistance are not in scope.

Insurers can be framed as acting as either risk carriers (reducing financial impacts of risk and supporting resilient outcomes) or risk managers (where an insurer actively steps into manage risks via advisory or risk modelling etc.) (UNEP, 2024). The compendium focuses on the role that insurers play as risk carriers. Furthermore, the compendium does not consider other roles that insurers can play towards generating nature-positive outcomes, such as via charitable support through their foundations or insurers who divert a portion of their premiums or profit towards nature-positive causes/interventions (NatureSave, n.d.; Planet Protection, n.d.).

Literature and guidance collection. Inclusion criteria prioritised resources that map how nature loss creates risks and opportunities for insurers, quantify the link between ecosystem condition and insured losses, or provide practical tools for integrating nature into insurance assessment and product design. These are drawn from both NATURANCE deliverables and external publications across the insurance, conservation and policy sectors. This report presents a cross-sectional selection of foundational resources. Additional material is available in the [digital library](#), including country-specific and academic publications.

Case study collection and selection. Case studies were collected through multiple channels: shared by organisations including UNEP FI and ORRAA, submitted via a survey from members of the NATURANCE knowledge network, and manual research by the project team. To qualify for inclusion, each entry must meet the nature-related insurance product definition above and have sufficient public documentation to describe its details and scope. All entries were screened against these criteria. Out of the 47 case studies identified, this report presents a curated subset of 21 case studies selected to illustrate the breadth of products and their different applications.

1.4 Limitations

The compendium does not present an exhaustive inventory of nature-related insurance products or guidance. Case studies were gathered through NATURANCE partners, expert submissions and manual research, meaning the collection is shaped by the networks and channels through which information was sourced. Products that are not publicly documented, that operate in languages not covered by the research team, or that were launched after the collection period closed may be absent. The digital library should therefore be treated as an indicative rather than comprehensive snapshot of the market at the time of writing.

Several aspects of the analysis rely on judgement-based classification. Fields such as insurance product type, broader risk addressed, and SDG and GBF alignment were coded manually on the basis of available documentation, and different analysts may reasonably have assigned different values in borderline cases. While entries with insufficient public documentation were excluded from the compendium, the level of detail available varied across case studies, which may affect the consistency of tagging across the library. Readers should interpret the quantitative patterns reported in [Section 4](#) as indicative of broad trends rather than precise measurements of market composition.

2. Compendium of Guidance on Nature and Insurance

This section showcases NATURANCE guidance in the context of the wider market, bringing together the key guidance and literature available to practitioners working at the intersection of nature and insurance. It is split into two parts. [Section 2.1](#) presents the outputs of the NATURANCE project itself, including nine Innovation Labs and five supporting deliverables that together offer co-designed solutions, technical methods and policy recommendations. [Section 2.2](#) curates key external publications from across the insurance, conservation and policy sectors that complement and extend those findings.

Refer to [Annex B](#) for a full list of the fields and definitions that were used to structure the summaries of the guidance.

2.1 Naturance Deliverables and Guidance

The NATURANCE project examined how the insurance sector can support the uptake of nature-based solutions, exploring opportunities across both underwriting and investment activities. Through a series of nine Innovation Labs convened across Europe, the project brought together insurers, reinsurers, policymakers, local authorities, landowners and researchers to co-design practical solutions tailored to specific hazards and contexts. This stakeholder-driven approach proved to be an innovation in itself, generating insights that would not have emerged from siloed research or consultation.

The deliverables presented in this section address interconnected challenges: how risk transfer mechanisms can complement and incentivise risk reduction through NbS; how equity considerations could be embedded into scheme designs; how improved methods can better quantify the risk-reduction potential and co-benefits of NbS for insurance pricing; and what policy and governance reforms are needed to mainstream these approaches. Together, these outputs provide both conceptual frameworks and practical guidance for integrating nature into insurance and broader climate resilience finance.

Section 2.1 Navigation Table — NATURANCE Deliverables & Guidance

Use this table to find outputs relevant to your topic, role and expertise level.

REF	RESOURCE	REGION	TOPIC	TYPE	AUDIENCE	LEVEL
Innovation Labs						

2.1.1	Innovation Lab 1 – Natural flood management	UK	Flood	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.2	Innovation Lab 2 – Flood risk quantification	Netherlands	Flood	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Expert
2.1.3	Innovation Lab 3 – Wildfire insurance & NbS	EU/Mediterranean	Wildfire	Co-designed solutions	Intl Orgs, Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.4	Innovation Lab 4 – Insurance as investment enabler	Global	Investment	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.5	Innovation Lab 5 – Urban heat financing	London, UK	Heat	Co-designed solutions	Civil Society, Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.6	Innovation Lab 6 – Controlled flooding insurance	Italy	Flood	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.7	Innovation Lab 7 – Protected area investment	Europe	Conservation finance	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.8	Innovation Lab 8 – Urban NbS resilience finance	Europe	Urban / Green infra	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.9	Innovation Lab 9 – Wetland restoration financing	Sweden	Wetlands	Co-designed solutions	Private, Public	● Intermediate
Supporting Deliverables						
2.1.10	Think pieces (D2.4)	Global	Cross-cutting	Policy report	Intl Orgs, Private, Public	● Beginner
2.1.11	Equitable & Sustainable Business Models (D3.2)	Global	Equity & design	Working paper	Private, Public	● Intermediate
2.1.12	Policy directions & governance reforms (D3.3)	EU	Policy & regulation	Policy report	Public	● Beginner
2.1.13	Improved methods for risk reduction (D4.2)	Netherlands	Modelling & valuation	Working paper	Civil Society, Private, Public	● Expert
2.1.14	Integrating NbS in insurance schemes (D4.3)	Netherlands	Insurance design	Working paper	Civil Society, Private, Public	● Expert

2.1.1 Innovation Lab 1: Investing in natural flood management in urban areas in the UK — LSE (2024)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2024	Academic Research	United Kingdom	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	LSE, Flood Re

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by LSE, explored how England's Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) legislation could unlock investment in natural flood management in urban areas, addressing the rising risk of coastal, surface and riverine flooding threatening the UK's housing stock.

Running in 2024, the lab convened insurers, local councils, mortgage lenders, and solution providers to develop a business case showing how mandatory biodiversity requirements can finance green infrastructure, such as wetlands and parks, that provide both flood protection and ecosystem co-benefits. In collaboration with Flood Re, the lab examined the applicability of BNG principles to boost flood resilience in urban environments. Key findings include:

- 1) BNG funding sources could be targeted at existing urban flood risk management plans, benefiting from their established monitoring frameworks;
- 2) The insurance sector can play an important role through novel products that de-risk BNG investments, reward NbS co-benefits, or insure natural capital to catalyse its repair and recovery post-flooding; and
- 3) Care is needed to ensure that a focus on natural flood management does not come at the expense of biodiversity.

This lab demonstrated how regulatory requirements like BNG and risk transfer solutions could boost climate resilience through natural flood management. Key outputs include a report and scorecard published on the NATURANCE website, and a policy report co-authored with Flood Re focusing on BNG and urban flood risk management.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · [Report](#) · [Webinar](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.2 Innovation Lab 2: Methods to quantify flood risk reduction and co-benefits of NbS in the Netherlands - VU-IVM (2024)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2024	Academic Research	Limburg, The Netherlands	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Expert	IVM, Dutch Insurance Association, Rabobank, Rijkwaterstaat, Municipality of Valkenburg

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by VU-IVM, explored methods to quantify the flood risk reduction potential and co-benefits of NbS in the Netherlands, using the 2021 Limburg floods as a case study.

Across three sessions between November 2023 and April 2024, the lab convened insurers, banks, local government and academic experts to examine how enhanced catastrophe models could better capture NbS impacts on insurance premiums and explored choice experiment design with local stakeholders. Key solutions include:

- 1) Developing object-based hydrological models that can assess NbS at building scale, providing the granularity needed for insurance pricing;
- 2) Integrating climate adaptation measures into Dynamic Integrated Flood Insurance (DIFI) models to reflect NbS benefits in premium calculations; and
- 3) Public-private partnerships emerged as the most promising financing mechanism for NbS, addressing challenges such as free-riding and investment risk that deter purely private-sector involvement.

This lab demonstrated how improved risk assessment methods could inform investment decisions and potentially enhance insurability in flood-prone areas. Outputs include a report and scorecard, with an additional paper on assessing NbS risk reduction and its co-benefits for insurance models.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · [Assessing NbS Risk Reduction](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.3 Innovation Lab 3: Harnessing insurance to promote nature-based solutions for wildfire risk management - IIASA (2024)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2024	Academic Research	EU, particularly Mediterranean region	Intl Organisations, Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	IIASA, Firelogue, EIOPA, Marsh McLennan, WTW, Forest Re, Swiss Re, AXA, MITIGA Solutions, World Bank, OECD, TUD, CTFC, Green Insurance Association

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by IIASA, explored how insurance mechanisms could support NbS for wildfire risk management, with a focus on closing the wildfire insurance protection gap in the EU, especially in Mediterranean countries.

Across three sessions between July 2023 and May 2024, the lab convened insurers, brokers, regulators (including EIOPA), ecologists and policymakers to examine current wildfire insurance landscapes, NbS approaches, and how insurers could financially incentivise more sustainable forest management. Key solutions identified include:

- 1) Community-based insurance models inspired by the US NFIP's Community Rating System could incentivise proactive wildfire risk reduction through NbS;
- 2) Incorporating NbS into parametric wildfire insurance pricing could yield premium reductions of 20–43%, making sustainable forest management financially attractive; and
- 3) Reforming the EU Solidarity Fund to incentivise Member State investment in NbS, alongside a taxonomy of insurer activities for enabling NbS spread across underwriting and investment.

This lab generated actionable recommendations for EU and national regulators on differentiated pricing for NbS, parametric product transparency and adopting the TNFD as a risk framework. Outputs include a report, scorecard and policy briefs targeting European policymakers.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.4 Innovation Lab 4: How can insurance be an enabler to catalyse investment into nature-based projects? - CISL (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Global	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	CISL, ClimateWise, ABI, AON, AXA, Beazley, Flood Re, Howden, Inigo Insurance, Liberty, QBE, RenaissanceRe, WTW, ManuLife, Rathbones, PensionFonds PGB, Robeco, State Street, UBP, Zurich Re, ABN-AMRO, Deutsche Bank, HSBC, NatWest, Santander, Standard Chartered

DESCRIPTION

Hosted by CISL in collaboration with the ClimateWise insurance network, this lab explored how insurance can catalyse investment into nature-based projects, taking a strategic sector-wide approach rather than focusing on specific hazards.

Across three workshops between February and June 2024, the lab convened insurers, reinsurers, brokers, banks and asset managers to map the current insurance landscape, identify where new product development is needed, and explore emerging innovative financial mechanisms. Through this exercise, six areas of focus were identified: collaboration, risk mitigation, data, financial innovation, value analysis and community empowerment. Key solutions include:

- 1) Encouraging insurers to share NbS costs with banks and other financial institutions to spread risk and align incentives;
- 2) Developing shared data and modelling standards for NbS to overcome the current lack of consistent metrics;
- 3) Better quantifying the co-benefits of NbS to strengthen the investment case and attract diverse funders; and
- 4) A phased roadmap for implementing innovative financing models, supported by 20 real-world examples of insurance roles in NbS projects.

This lab demonstrated the value of cross-sector dialogue in overcoming barriers to NbS investment, moving beyond the confines of specific hazard types.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.5 Innovation Lab 5: Financing for heat action plans at city-level in Europe - WTW (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	London, United Kingdom	Civil Society, Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	WTW, Greater London Authority, L.B. Southwark, St. Mungo's, Shade the UK, Oxford University

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by WTW, explored financing mechanisms for urban heat action plans, focusing on trigger-based financing instruments and parametric insurance to address the critical gap in dedicated heat risk funding.

Across three workshops between November 2024 and February 2025, the lab convened urban planners, local government officials, climate scientists and insurers to examine financial, data and governance barriers to heat preparedness and response, with London as the primary case study. Two use cases were explored: applying trigger-based financing to the existing Hot Weather Severe Weather Emergency Protocol for rough sleepers, and using risk analytics to manage heatwave impacts on urban green spaces. Key findings include:

- 1) Trigger-based financing is better suited to beneficiary groups requiring immediate response funding, such as emergency services for vulnerable populations;
- 2) NbS and green spaces require longer-term investment rather than short-term payouts, though parametric products could potentially support post-heatwave restoration of natural assets; and
- 3) Implementation requires further engagement with local authorities and improved hyper-local temperature data to ensure products are accurately calibrated.

This lab demonstrated the potential for risk-informed financing structures to improve heat emergency response, while highlighting that different types of nature-based and social interventions require distinct financing approaches.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.6 Innovation Lab 6: Boosting flood resilience in Italy through controlled flooding, community insurance and nature-based solutions - CMCC (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Po River basin, Italy	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	CMCC, ANBI, Assicurazioni Generali, AdBPo, IVASS, Banca d'Italia

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by CMCC, explored an innovative community-based parametric insurance scheme for controlled flooding operations at the river basin level, designed to enhance flood resilience in Northern Italy's Po River Basin District.

Across three sessions between October 2024 and February 2025, the lab convened water boards, regional authorities, insurers and financial regulators to assess the operational, regulatory and financial feasibility of a scheme where water boards purchase collective insurance to cover controlled flooding costs, funded through community contributions. Key design features and findings include:

- 1) The parametric insurance product features triggers linked to precipitation thresholds, enabling rapid payouts for planned flood management operations;
- 2) Because controlled flooding requires upstream rural land to be converted to NbS for water retention, the scheme explored mechanisms to compensate landowners for agricultural loss and incentivise NbS adoption; and
- 3) Existing water board classification plans were identified as a tool to ensure equitable cost distribution between upstream rural landowners (who bear the burden) and downstream urban beneficiaries.

This lab demonstrated how community-based insurance can shift flood risk management from reactive compensation to proactive risk reduction. The proposal secured Network Nature Labs funding for international expansion.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.7 Innovation Lab 7: Promoting a network of protected areas to support biodiversity and ecosystem functioning: an opportunity for nature conservation investments? - KIT (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Europe	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	KIT, Invest4Nature, GoNaturePositive!, SUPERB, NaturaConnect, BIO-CAPITAL, REST-COAST, REWRITE, Highlands Rewilding, GreenBox, CO2eco, EIB

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by KIT, explored investment opportunities in nature conservation within the EU's protected area network, aiming to stimulate private investment to complement public funding and bridge the nature conservation financing gap.

Across three sessions between April and July 2025, the lab convened researchers, private sector actors and partners from related EU projects to map financial instruments, identify barriers and explore enabling conditions for scaling private investment in protected areas. Key enabling conditions identified include:

- 1) De-risking investments through public-private partnerships and blending funding sources (such as grants, equity and private finance) for long-term sustainability;
- 2) Leveraging ESG frameworks for transparency and promoting local value creation through territorial branding and community-based business models; and
- 3) Insurance was noted as a potential mechanism to support risk management, though engagement remains limited by short-term contract cycles that misalign with the long-term nature of conservation investments.

This lab produced a Business Model Canvas consolidating value propositions, instruments, barriers and enabling conditions to guide nature-positive investments, emphasising that context-specific, multi-instrument approaches are essential.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.8 Innovation Lab 8: Advancing Nature-based Solutions through Innovative Resilience Finance - ICLEI (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Europe	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	ICLEI, Ruhr Regional Association, Budapest, Gdańsk, Brussels, Utrecht, Aarhus, Poznań, BwB, EIB, Howden, Climate-KIC, Green Cities Partnership, EUI, Invest4Nature

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by ICLEI Europe, explored how innovative resilience finance mechanisms can unlock investment in urban NbS and green infrastructure, targeting local authorities, insurers, finance professionals and policymakers.

Across three sessions between May and July 2025, the lab convened cities, financial institutions and insurers to identify barriers and enablers for green infrastructure financing and explore innovative mechanisms including public-private partnerships and insurance. A distinctive "pitch session" format allowed cities to present their NbS projects directly to a panel of finance and insurance experts for live feedback. Key outcomes include:

- 1) Insurers and financial stakeholders emphasised the need for flexible financing schemes, quantification of co-benefits to attract diverse funders, and clear visualisations to promote projects to investors;
- 2) Early engagement with insurers during project design phases was identified as critical to addressing potential risks before they become barriers; and
- 3) Real urban initiatives from Gdańsk, Utrecht, Poznań and Aarhus showcased approaches such as corporate sponsorship, crowdplanting and blended finance models.

This lab successfully connected cities with finance and insurance experts, generating practical recommendations and fostering new collaborations including ongoing discussions between cities and insurers.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.9 Innovation Lab 9: Wetland restoration as NbS: Management and financing needs - SU (2025)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Sweden	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	Stockholm University, Restoration Projects, Swedish Geological Survey, KTH, Lund University, Halmstad University, Rural Economy and Agricultural Society of Halland, Insurance Sweden, WRS Consulting

DESCRIPTION

This Lab, led by Stockholm University, examined the management and financing needs required to catalyse wetland restoration as NbS in Sweden, assessing whether restored wetlands can deliver multiple ecosystem services.

Across three sessions between June and September 2025, the lab convened landowners, municipalities, county administrative boards, NGOs, researchers and insurance specialists to identify barriers and explore financing pathways. Sessions focused on Swedish regional perspectives before broadening to comparative EU experiences and alternative finance models. Key findings include:

- 1) Base funding availability is no longer the primary constraint in Sweden, rather, landowners hesitate due to long-term risks including liability concerns, potential flooding and technical failure;
- 2) Insurance emerged as a critical potential solution pathway, particularly tailored products covering NbS malfunction and reduced premiums for common goods provision; and
- 3) Context-specific packages combining demonstration sites, monitoring, insurance and compensation are required to lower entry barriers for small and medium landowners and unlock private finance.

This lab produced a feasibility heatmap assessing solution combinations needed to address identified challenges, emphasising that no single instrument is sufficient and that bundled approaches are essential.

SOURCES

[Scorecard](#) · *Training Module [TBC]*

2.1.10 Think pieces: NbS opportunities for risk transfer & investment (D2.4)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Policy Report	Global	Intl Organisations, Private Sector, Public Sector	● Beginner	NATURANCE Consortium

DESCRIPTION

This deliverable, led by CISL, presents a series of public-facing briefs and insight pieces designed to translate NATURANCE findings into accessible guidance for policymakers and finance professionals, building on specific threads from the project's Innovation Labs.

The briefs address four topical challenges:

- 1) How risk transfer can enable NbS uptake while ensuring equitable distribution of costs and benefits across stakeholders;
- 2) Pathways to scale private investment in NbS given heavy reliance on public funding;
- 3) Improved methods to quantify and monetise NbS co-benefits, addressing current undervaluation that leads to underinvestment; and
- 4) Enhanced flood risk modelling that incorporates NbS effects at catchment scale for more accurate insurance pricing. Complementary insight pieces explore parametric insurance for coastal ecosystems and the potential of England's Biodiversity Net Gain legislation for urban flood management.

Together, these outputs form a public-facing legacy for NATURANCE, providing practitioners with actionable insights on integrating NbS into insurance, risk transfer and investment frameworks.

SOURCES

Policy Briefs [TBD]

2.1.11 Equitable and Sustainable Business Models (D3.2)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Working Paper	Global	Private Sector, Public Sector	● Intermediate	NATURANCE Consortium

DESCRIPTION

This deliverable, led by LSE, explores how insurance schemes can be designed to incorporate equity and environmental sustainability, examining design considerations such as risk reduction linkages, premium subsidisation and parametric versus indemnity structures, while introducing equity as a further consideration given insurance's expanding role in addressing societal challenges.

The report acknowledges there is no universal blueprint for embedding equity and nature into insurance schemes. Drawing on five case studies, it contextualises how principles from established equity frameworks are embedded into scheme design. Key insights include:

- 1) Schemes exist in multiple configurations of public, private and third sector actors;
- 2) Stakeholder engagement varies significantly and influences whom schemes serve;
- 3) Nature is often considered secondary to climate objectives; and
- 4) Balancing multiple equity principles can pull schemes in different directions.

The report concludes that success requires revisiting foundational assumptions, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and designing solutions that are principled yet pragmatic. Key challenges include defining vulnerability across intersecting dimensions, reconciling diverse equity perspectives across roles, and building trust through meaningful community participation.

SOURCES

[Report](#) · [Blog \(1\)](#) · [Blog \(2\)](#)

2.1.12 Transformative policy directions and governance reforms (D3.3)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Policy Report	EU	Public Sector	● Beginner	NATURANCE Consortium

DESCRIPTION

This deliverable, led by CMCC, examines transformative policy directions and governance reforms that support climate adaptation, focusing on the role of NbS in insurance and finance.

The report provides a stocktake of current policies and frameworks relevant to NbS, grouped thematically: sustainable insurance principles and regulatory guidance (e.g., EIOPA's work on climate risk and protection gaps); climate and nature-related disclosure frameworks (e.g., TNFD); sustainable finance instruments and standards (e.g., EU Taxonomy); and emerging mechanisms (e.g., nature credits). While momentum is growing, the analysis reveals persistent gaps in regulatory alignment, incentives, and implementation capacity.

Through horizon scanning, three emerging trends are identified:

- 1) Financial protection against climate-related losses is increasingly recognised as a public resilience goal;
- 2) Nature is progressively framed as a bankable and insurable asset; and
- 3) Risk governance is shifting from centralised approaches toward place-based, locally-led solutions.

The report concludes that advancing NbS as a core pillar of climate adaptation will require coordinated reforms aligning financial and regulatory frameworks with long-term risk reduction, recognising nature as a critical resilience asset, and ensuring benefits and responsibilities are distributed fairly.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.1.13 Improved methods for the assessment of risk reduction achieved by NBS for insurance and for assessing co-benefits to society (D4.2)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Working Paper	Limburg, The Netherlands	Civil Society, Private Sector, Public Sector	Expert	VU-IVM

DESCRIPTION

This deliverable, led by VU, develops improved metrics and methods for assessing the risk-reduction potential and co-benefits of NbS, illustrated through the case study of the 2021 European floods in Limburg, the Netherlands.

The report addresses key methodological gaps through stakeholder co-design, grouping improvements into: risk-reduction assessment (developing an object-level catastrophe model coupling hydrological and NbS modelling); physical co-benefits modelling (ecosystem services and long-term effectiveness under climate change); and monetary co-benefits valuation (a choice experiment survey with over 2,000 respondents). Key methodological insights include:

- 1) Co-creation with insurers, policymakers and local stakeholders ensures assessments address real-world needs and increases policy relevance of results;
- 2) Significant variation in NbS performance highlights the need for differentiated approaches when monetising co-benefits; and
- 3) A tension emerges between stated NbS preferences and willingness to convert land, as respondents favour reforestation yet show reluctance to give up agricultural land required for its implementation.

The report concludes that combining risk-reduction metrics with monetised co-benefits through social cost-benefit analysis can strengthen the investment case for NbS, informing financing strategies for both public and private sectors.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.1.14 Recommendations for integrating NbS in insurance schemes based on the synthesized and improved catastrophe models and other methods and empirical evidence base (D4.3)

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Working Paper	The Netherlands	Civil Society, Private Sector, Public Sector	Expert	NATURANCE Consortium

DESCRIPTION

This deliverable, led by VU, provides recommendations for mainstreaming investment in Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for climate risk reduction, with a focus on how insurance can contribute to scaling up NbS adoption.

The report synthesises findings from improved flood risk modelling, co-benefits assessment, and insurance modelling applied to the 2021 European floods case study in Limburg. It reviews financial instruments for NbS investment, drawing on expert assessment through Innovation Labs, and proposes shared metrics and standards for evaluating NbS performance. Key findings include:

- 1) Co-benefits assessment is essential for demonstrating the economic viability of NbS, particularly for large-scale interventions requiring significant land conversion;
- 2) Public-private partnerships emerged as the preferred financing mechanism, with insurance schemes, green bonds and grants also ranking highly among experts;
- 3) Land acquisition costs represent a critical barrier, suggesting that mixed-use arrangements combining agriculture with NbS could improve both financial feasibility and social acceptance; and
- 4) Under public-private insurance arrangements, insurers can achieve attractive returns (10–20% annually) by investing in NbS proportional to risk reduction generated.

The report concludes with recommendations including employing shared metrics for comparability, integrating NbS into spatially detailed catastrophe models, and fostering public-private collaboration to align risk reduction benefits with financing mechanisms.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2 External Literature and Guidance

There has been an upward trend over the last few years in publications exploring how nature and insurance can interact. This section summarises emerging guidance from sister projects across the EU, insurers or other global organisations to map the broader landscape and situate NATURANCE's contributions. It presents 15 publications from across the insurance, conservation and policy sectors that complement the NATURANCE deliverables and guidance.

Section 2.2 Navigation Table — External Literature & Guidance

Key publications from across the insurance, conservation and policy sectors.

REF	PUBLICATION	YEAR	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	WHY IT MATTERS
2.2.1	Geneva Association – Nature & the insurance industry	2022	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Industry framing of nature loss as a business risk</i>
2.2.2	WWF/Deloitte – Underwriting our planet	2023	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Maps underwriting activities to drivers of nature loss</i>
2.2.3	EDF – Nature for insurance & insurance for nature	2025	Private, Public	☉ Intermediate	<i>Identifies barriers to scaling and priority policy areas</i>
2.2.4	UNEP FI – Insuring a nature-positive future	2024	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>First global roadmap for insurers on biodiversity</i>
2.2.5	Howden/Pollination – Through the Wilderness	2024	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Frames insurance as an enabler of private nature finance</i>
2.2.6	Swiss Re – BES Index	2020	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Global tool linking ecosystem condition to insurable risks</i>
2.2.7	Invest4Nature – Insurance value of NbS	2025	Public	☼ Expert	<i>Evidence that NbS investments lower insured losses</i>
2.2.8	WWF – Tackling the insurance protection gap	2025	Private, Public	☉ Intermediate	<i>Quantifies how nature loss widens the protection gap</i>
2.2.9	TNC/WTW – Wildfire Resilience Insurance	2021	Public, Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Quantifies premium savings from ecological forest management</i>
2.2.10	Munich Re/TNC – Nature's remedy	2021	Public, Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>First insurance pricing model for nature-based flood reduction</i>
2.2.11	UNEP FI – Rooted in Risk	2025	Private	☼ Expert	<i>Technical basis for nature risks in underwriting portfolios</i>
2.2.12	UNEP FI – Breaking Ground	2025	Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Hands-on TNFD LEAP guidance for insurance</i>
2.2.13	UNDP – Insurance for nature-related risks	2025	Intl Orgs, Public	☉ Beginner	<i>Helps countries integrate insurance into national biodiversity finance plans</i>
2.2.14	Earth Security – Insurance Underwriting With Nature	2022	Public, Private	☉ Intermediate	<i>Mangrove insurance pilots with demonstrated real-world uptake</i>

2.2.15	Marsh McLennan – Rooted in Resilience: Innovations in Nature Insurance for Business	2023	Private	⦿ Intermediate	<i>Links nature loss to corporate balance sheet risks and maps insurance responses</i>
<i>Please note, the external literature and guidance highlighted in this document represents a curated subset of a larger collection which can be viewed in the NATURANCE digital library.</i>					

The publications highlighted here represent a subset, selected to cover a range of perspectives, audiences and solutions spanning insurers, policymakers and environmental organisations, of a broader collection of relevant literature which can be accessed in the NATURANCE [digital library](#).

Please refer to [Annex B](#) for full definitions for all fields and their values.

2.2.1 Nature and the Insurance Industry: Taking action towards a nature-positive economy					
YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2022	Policy Report	Global	Private Sector	⦿ Intermediate	The Geneva Association
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This industry association report provides a strategic overview of how nature loss creates risks and opportunities for insurers, covering the science of biodiversity decline, the climate-nature feedback loop, and external pressures from regulation, litigation, and investor expectations. It finds that while nature-related underwriting and investment solutions are emerging, such as parametric reef insurance in the Caribbean, they remain far from sufficient scale.</p> <p>The report argues that insurers depend on healthy ecosystems to keep risks insurable, and that their unique expertise in risk assessment and risk transfer positions them well to develop financial products that protect and restore natural systems while opening new lines of business.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.2 Underwriting our planet: how insurers can help address the crises in climate and biodiversity

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2023	Policy Report	Global	Private Sector	Intermediate	WWF, Deloitte
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This report maps how non-life insurance underwriting activities connect to the five main drivers of biodiversity loss, including land-use change, pollution, and climate change. It finds that insurers have largely overlooked their responsibility for the environmental impacts of the activities they make possible, and that significant opportunities exist to redesign products, exclude harmful activities, and incentivise sustainable behaviour.</p> <p>The report explains that without insurance, many environmentally damaging activities like fossil fuel extraction and industrial shipping could not operate at current scale, meaning insurers hold real but underused leverage to accelerate the transition to a nature-positive economy.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.3 Nature for Insurance and Insurance for Nature

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Policy Report	United States	Private Sector, Public Sector	Intermediate	Environmental Defense Fund
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Based on a workshop of nearly 100 experts, this report explores the two-way relationship between nature and insurance. Natural systems like wetlands and forests reduce disaster losses that stress insurance markets, while insurers can use their underwriting, pricing, investment, and advocacy tools to drive nature-positive outcomes across the economy. It finds that despite growing interest, few implemented approaches have yet achieved meaningful scale, and key barriers remain in integrating nature into catastrophe models and securing localised data.</p> <p>The report argues that stabilising insurance markets long-term requires investing in nature-based risk reduction, and that insurance's reach across virtually every economic sector makes it a uniquely powerful lever for protecting nature in return.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.4 Insuring a resilient nature-positive future: Global guide for insurers on setting priority actions for nature

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2024	Implementation Guide	Global	Private Sector	Intermediate	UNEP FI, PSI Working Group for Nature
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This is the first global guide giving insurers a practical roadmap for aligning their business with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework's goal of halting nature loss by 2030. It covers both non-life and life and health insurers, outlining priority actions across the insurance value chain from product design to client engagement.</p> <p>The guide frames insurers in a dual role, as enablers of economic activities that can harm nature and as managers of emerging risks from nature loss. By connecting specific insurance business lines to nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities, it provides a structured pathway for the industry to move from awareness to meaningful action on biodiversity.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.5 Through the Wilderness: The Role of Insurance in Unlocking Nature Finance

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2024	Corporate Publication	Global	Private Sector	Intermediate	Howden, Pollination
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This report argues that the insurance sector can play a transformative role in scaling the private finance needed to meet global biodiversity and climate goals, which require nature finance to triple by 2030. It identifies four key roles for insurers, including delivering risk transfer solutions for environmental markets, adapting crop insurance for regenerative agriculture, and incentivising habitat restoration and conservation. It finds that emerging experience in forests, coastal systems, and agriculture shows growing but still nascent capacity across the sector.</p> <p>The report frames insurance not just as a passive responder to nature-related losses but as an active enabler that can reduce investment barriers, build investor confidence, and accelerate capital flows towards nature-positive activities.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.6 Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services: A business case for re/insurance

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2020	Corporate Publication	Global	Private Sector	Intermediate	Swiss Re
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Swiss Re introduces its Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Index, a global tool measuring ecosystem health at a one-square-kilometre resolution across ten services including pollination, erosion control, and coastal protection. The report finds that 55% of global GDP depends moderately or highly on ecosystem services, and that one-fifth of countries have ecosystems in a fragile state across more than 30% of their territory.</p> <p>This has direct implications for insurers because disappearing forests lead to rising landslide and flood claims, deteriorating air quality drives up health insurance costs, and degraded coastlines leave properties more exposed to storms. The index gives the industry a concrete way to measure and price these risks.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.7 Economic & financial performance of Nature-based Solutions, including the insurance value of NbS

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Academic Research	Europe	Public Sector	Expert	Invest4Nature, Aarhus University, CMCC, JR, NIVA
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This EU-funded research report examines whether nature-based solutions like river restoration and wetland rewilding deliver good economic returns, with a particular focus on their ability to reduce financial losses from floods and other disasters. Drawing on 381 European studies and two detailed cases in Austria and Portugal, it finds that these investments generally pay for themselves, with the Portuguese case showing a 43% reduction in flood damage to buildings.</p> <p>The report argues that its findings carry direct implications for the insurance sector, showing that investing in nature measurably lowers the disaster losses that ultimately flow through to insurance claims. It concludes that nature's risk-reduction value is significantly underpriced in current economic and financial models, and that integrating this "insurance value" into decision-making could help unlock the investment needed to scale up nature-based solutions.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.8 Tackling the Insurance Protection Gap: Leveraging Climate Mitigation and Nature to Increase Resilience

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Working Paper	Global	Private Sector, Public Sector	🌀 Intermediate	WWF
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This WWF white paper analyses how climate change and nature destruction are widening the gap between economic losses from extreme weather and insurance coverage, with a focus on the EU, UK and US. The protection gap averaged \$64 billion per year in the US (2021-2024) and €59 billion per year in the EU (2021-2023), while degraded ecosystems dramatically worsen outcomes: deforestation can increase large-scale flood risk by up to 700%.</p> <p>The report traces how rising uninsured losses cascade into mortgage markets, household wealth, business competitiveness and public finances, creating systemic threats to economic stability. It argues that nature-based solutions should be central to adaptation and resilience planning, noting that Switzerland's protective forests provide \$4.5 billion in annual value and can be up to 25 times more cost-effective than engineered alternatives.</p> <p>Recommendations call on governments and insurers to cut emissions, halt nature loss, and embed ecosystem restoration into insurance regulation and disaster recovery frameworks.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.2.9 Wildfire Resilience Insurance: Quantifying the Risk Reduction of Ecological Forestry with Insurance

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2021	Policy Report	United States	Public Sector, Private Sector	🌀 Intermediate	The Nature Conservancy, WTW
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This report uses catastrophe modelling to measure how ecological forest management: prescribed burns and thinning of overgrown vegetation, reduces wildfire risk and insurance costs. Using a case study in California's Tahoe National Forest, it finds that ecological forestry could cut residential insurance premiums by 41% for 81,000 homes, saving \$21 million annually. It also pilots a new parametric insurance product for wildfire intensity and acreage. These premium savings could be recycled to fund further forest restoration, creating a self-reinforcing cycle where nature-based risk reduction directly improves the affordability and availability of insurance in fire-prone areas.</p>					

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.10 Nature's remedy: Improving flood resilience through community insurance and nature-based mitigation

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2021	Working Paper	United States	Public Sector, Private Sector	● Intermediate	Munich Re, The Nature Conservancy

DESCRIPTION

This study examines whether nature-based flood mitigation can be combined with community-level insurance to reduce both flood risk and insurance costs along inland rivers in the United States. Using a levee setback project on the Missouri River as a case study, it finds that restoring floodplain functions measurably lowers water levels during floods and reduces the likelihood of catastrophic events, which in turn translates to lower insurance premiums.

This was the first time nature-based river flood reduction had been quantified in insurance modelling and pricing terms. The authors propose a replicable model where premium savings from nature-based interventions help fund further restoration projects across the Mississippi River Basin and beyond.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.11 Rooted in Risk: Framing nature-related assessments for insurers

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Policy Report	Global	Private Sector	● Expert	UNEP FI, PSI Working Group for Nature

DESCRIPTION

This technical guidance helps insurers understand where nature-related issues affect their business and how to begin assessing them systematically. Building on the 2024 priority actions guide, it maps how nature risks materialise across different insurance lines of business for both non-life and life and health companies. It finds that while awareness of nature-related risk is growing among insurers, most lack the frameworks and data to conduct meaningful assessments.

The report demonstrates that nature-related dependencies and impacts are already embedded throughout insurers' underwriting portfolios, from agriculture and construction to health, and provides the analytical basis needed to identify, prioritise, and respond to them effectively.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.12 Breaking Ground: Getting practical with nature-related assessments for insurers

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Implementation Guide	Global	Private Sector	● Intermediate	UNEP FI, PSI Working Group for Nature

DESCRIPTION

This is the second report in the UNEP FI "Nature Uncovered for Insurers" series, moving from the conceptual framing of its predecessor "Rooted in Risk" into hands-on guidance for conducting nature-related assessments. Drawing on experiences from insurers worldwide, it shows how companies can apply the TNFD's LEAP approach to their underwriting portfolios and begin evaluating nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities.

It offers practical use cases and guidance for insurers at different stages of readiness. The report fills a critical gap because while nature assessment frameworks exist across finance, dedicated methods for insurance underwriting portfolios have been largely absent until now.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.13 How Insurance Can Address Nature-related Risks: A Summary Guide

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2025	Implementation Guide	Global	Public Sector, Intl Organisations	● Beginner	UNDP BIOFIN, UNDP IRFF, AB Entheos

DESCRIPTION

This guide helps developing countries consider insurance as a tool within their national biodiversity finance plans, explaining core concepts and providing a decision-support framework for when insurance is the right mechanism. It highlights global examples including reef insurance, wildlife conflict coverage in Kenya, and water fund insurance in Colombia, finding that a \$700 billion annual biodiversity finance gap demands creative financial tools.

Insurance fits into this picture as a versatile mechanism that can protect natural assets from damage, compensate communities affected by wildlife conflict, safeguard restoration investments, and incentivise conservation practices, yet it remains significantly underused in biodiversity finance strategies.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.14 Insurance Underwriting With Nature: How Mangroves Can Transform the Climate Strategy of Companies, Cities and Re/insurers

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2022	Policy Report	Philippines	Public Sector, Private Sector	 Intermediate	Earth Security

DESCRIPTION

Focusing on five coastal cities in the Philippines, this report demonstrates how mangrove forests reduce storm and flood damage and argues that this value should be factored into insurance underwriting and catastrophe modelling. It finds that mangroves can reduce annual property damage from extreme weather by up to 30% nationally, saving up to \$1 billion per year, and are 50 times more cost-effective than concrete seawalls.

The report makes the case that recognising mangroves as natural infrastructure in insurance policies would give insurers a competitive advantage through better-priced products while helping make otherwise uninsurable coastal assets viable.

SOURCES

[Report](#)

2.2.15 Rooted in Resilience: Innovations in Nature Insurance for Business

YEAR	TYPE	REGION	AUDIENCE	LEVEL	PARTNERS
2023	Corporate Publication	Global	Private Sector	● Intermediate	Marsh McLennan
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>This report explores how insurance solutions can support corporate environmental risk management as nature loss becomes increasingly material to business balance sheets, operations and value chains. It maps established products such as environmental impairment liability, directors' and officers', and business interruption insurance alongside emerging innovations including parametric covers for aquaculture, wildfire resilience, and carbon credit protection. It finds that while the market for nature-related risk transfer is growing, significant barriers remain in data availability, analytical tools and the identification of insurable interests for ecosystem-level risks.</p> <p>The report frames insurance not only as a tool for post-loss recovery but as a mechanism that can incentivise nature restoration, de-risk corporate decarbonisation strategies, and build resilience to physical climate risks, while setting out concrete actions for insurers, corporates and governments to bring these solutions to scale.</p>					
<p>SOURCES</p> <p>Report</p>					

2.3 Cross-cutting findings and recommendations

While the guidance reviewed in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 varies in scope, purpose and audience, consistent findings emerge across NATURANCE outputs and the wider literature regarding the actions needed to advance the role of nature-related insurance products. [Annex A](#) consolidates findings into five cross-cutting themes. For each, we outline the barriers identified, solutions being proposed or piloted, evidence from the nature-related insurance products collected in the [digital library \(Section 3\)](#), and recommendations for practitioners across the insurance, policy and conservation sectors.

The NATURANCE project has demonstrated that insurance can play a far more expansive role in facilitating the adoption of NbS. Across the Innovation Labs and supporting deliverables, a consistent finding was that effective integration of NbS into insurance requires collaboration across sectors, attention to who bears the costs and who receives the benefits, and robust methods to quantify and value what nature provides. The project advanced practical tools for quantifying NbS performance, explored novel product designs from community-based parametric schemes to investment de-risking mechanisms, and identified regulatory and governance shifts

needed to enable uptake at scale. Crucially, the co-design process itself surfaced solutions that balanced technical feasibility with multistakeholder representation. These contributions offer a foundation for policymakers, insurers and practitioners seeking to align risk transfer with risk reduction and to position nature as a core component of climate resilience strategy.

3. Compendium of Nature-related Insurance Products

This section presents case studies demonstrating how insurance products are being developed at the intersection of nature and climate and providing a snapshot of where the sector currently stands.

The compendium of nature-related insurance products (see definition: [Section 1.3](#)) contains profiles for 47 products identified.¹ Cases were gathered through NATURANCE partners as well as from experts across the insurance and conservation sectors via a public survey and contributions from external partners. The 21 case studies highlighted in this report represent a curated subset of the Compendium, while all 47 product entries can be accessed via the NATURANCE [digital library](#).

We gratefully acknowledge the organisations and individuals that shared case studies for inclusion in the compendium, including NATURANCE member organisations, UNEP FI and the ORRAA.

Cases are organised into three groups aligned with UNEP FI's Framework of Insurance Opportunities for Nature: Insurance for Nature Positive, Resilience Insurance and Transition Insurance. An overview of insurance products by category are visualised below in Figure 3.1.1.

UNEP FI framework of Insurance Opportunities for Nature:

Insurance for Nature Positive

Insurance solutions that protect natural assets or nature-based solutions, de-risk investments in conservation, restoration or sustainable nature use, or support the scaling of businesses delivering nature-positive outcomes.

¹ The NATURANCE Compendium aims to capture all nature-related insurance products for which sufficient public documentation is available. To qualify for inclusion, each entry must meet the nature-related insurance product definition (see [1.3](#)) and have sufficient public documentation to describe its details and scope. All 47 entries were screened against these criteria, though some may not have been identified.

Resilience Insurance

Insurance solutions that integrate nature-based approaches to risk reduction by reflecting the protective value of ecosystems in premium pricing or underwriting decisions. This also includes insurance that uses NbS to improve the availability or affordability of coverage, aid post-disaster recovery, or address emerging nature-related risks.

Transition Insurance

Insurance solutions which cover risks arising when businesses change their activities, operations or supply chains to reduce pressures on nature or achieve nature-positive outcomes.

(N.B. ‘Transition’ in this context refers to businesses changing their practices in relation to nature, as opposed to the ‘energy transition’).

Nature-related Insurance Products Identified in Compendium

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 3.1.1 Nature-related insurance products identified in the compendium

[Annex B](#) provides full definitions for all fields and their values. [Annex C](#) provides an overview of NATURANCE’s risk-based framework for insurance solutions and how it aligns with other lenses of viewing risks..

3.1 Insurance for Nature Positive

This category covers insurance products designed to protect nature, NbS and natural capital, sometimes referred to simply as "insurance for nature." It includes coverage during the construction and maturation of NbS projects, mechanisms to help ecosystems recover from damage, and products that de-risk investment in restoration and conservation activities. Examples range from parametric coral reef insurance that funds post-storm restoration to indemnity products protecting habitat banks and carbon credit investments.

The types of products which fall within this category are as follows:

3.1 Insurance for Nature Positive - Product types (adapted from UNEP FI)	
→	Insurance for conservation, restoration and NbS delivery, implementation, performance and management
→	Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature
→	Insurance to reduce risks to ecosystems and species
→	Insurance of natural assets
→	Insurance to remediate negative impacts on nature by prior or insured activities

Section 3.1 Navigation Table — Insurance for Nature Positive

Insurance solutions that protect natural assets or nature-based solutions, de-risk investments in conservation, restoration or sustainable nature use, or support the scaling of businesses delivering nature-positive outcomes.

REF	NAME	COUNTRY	REALM	TRIGGER TYPE	PRODUCT TYPE
3.1.1	Blue Bond Political Risk & Parametric Insurance — TNC, Credit Suisse (2021)	Belize	Marine	Indemnity	Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature
3.1.2	Prince Hendrik Sand Dyke Project — Swiss Re (2019)	Netherlands	Terrestria l	Indemnity	Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature
3.1.3	Offshore Asset Decommissioning Insurance — Hiscox, Lloyd's	Global	Marine	Indemnity	Insurance to remediate negative impacts on nature
3.1.4	Jaguar Protection Insurance — UNDP, Río Uruguay Seguros (2025)	Argentina	Terrestria l	Indemnity	Insurance to reduce risks to ecosystems and species

3.1.5	Habitat Banks Insurance — UNDP (2026)	Colombia	Terrestrial	Parametric /Index	Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature
3.1.6	Surf Ecosystem Insurance — Save The Waves, ORRAA (2024)	El Salvador	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance of natural assets
3.1.7	Marine Protected Area Insurance — AXA Climate, Howden (2023)	Philippines	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance of natural assets
3.1.8	San Crisanto Mangrove Insurance — AXA Climate, ClimateSeed (2023)	Mexico	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance of natural assets
3.1.9	Hawai'i Coral Reef Insurance — TNC, Munich Re (2024)	United States	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance of natural assets
3.1.10	Ping An Kelp/Seaweed Carbon Sink Insurance — Ping An P&C (2023)	China	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance of natural assets
3.1.11	Nature Restoration & Conservation Insurance Initiative — SCOR (2022)	Global	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for conservation, restoration & NbS delivery
3.1.12	GaiaSicura Ltd. — GaiaSicura, Lloyd's (2025)	Global	All	Indemnity	Insurance for conservation, restoration & NbS delivery; Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature
3.1.13	Community-led Mangrove Restoration through Green Life Insurance — Davivienda, FUNDEMAS (2019)	El Salvador	Marine	Indemnity	Insurance to reduce risks to ecosystems and species

Please note, the case studies highlighted in this document represent a curated subset of the full collection of nature-related insurance products. To view all cases, please visit the NATURANCE [digital library](#).

3.1.1 Political Risk and Parametric Catastrophe Insurance in relation to a Blue Bond for Ocean Conservation

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Belize	2021 – Unknown	Marine	Indemnity	Private Investors
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature		Public-Private-Partnership		Political and Sovereign Credit Risk	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>\$610 million in political risk insurance enabled a \$364 million Blue Bond for Ocean Conservation in Belize. This will generate an estimated \$90 million over 20 years to invest in marine and biodiversity protection and promote climate resilience in Belize's blue economy. The debt swap also introduced parametric catastrophe insurance to Belize's external debt stock at a cost of about \$800,000 per year on average for Belize.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		Government of Belize, The Nature Conservancy (TNC), Credit Suisse, Allianz, Munich Re, U.S. International Development Finance Corporation (DFC), BBIC SPV, NatureVest		Report	

3.1.2 Prince Hendrik Sand Dyke Project					
PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Completed	Netherlands	2019 – 2024	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Public Sector
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for conservation, restoration and NbS delivery, implementation, performance and management		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	
DESCRIPTION					
Construction all-risk coverage to support the restoration of the Prince Hendrick sand dyke that protects a unique ecosystem on the Island of Texel in the Netherlands – a World Heritage Site. The project aims to prevent a major failure of the dyke due to rising sea levels, while simultaneously improving biodiversity and protecting the local community, which benefits from physical protection afforded by the dyke and income from tourism and fishing.					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		Netherlands Coastline Care Programme, Swiss Re		Insurer Webpage	

3.1.3 Insurance for Decommissioning end of Life Offshore Assets

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Global	Unknown – Ongoing	Marine	Indemnity	Private - Real Economy, Private - Investors
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance to remediate negative impacts on nature by prior or insured activities		Private		Liability and Policy Risk	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Hiscox offers comprehensive third-party liability coverage for the decommissioning and removal of offshore assets, whether subsea or over-the-water. This cover is aimed at operators and other interests and enables them to remove end-of-life assets that could otherwise be environmentally damaging.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		Lloyd's, Hiscox		Article	

3.1.4 Jaguar Protection Insurance					
PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Argentina	2025 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance to reduce risks to ecosystems and species		Public-Private-Partnership		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>A pilot has been launched in Comandante Andresito, the municipality with the highest number of livestock losses due to jaguars in the Province of Misiones. The policy, purchased by the provincial government from Río Uruguay Seguros, covers cattle, pigs, sheep, goats, poultry, and pets (dogs and cats). It is provided free of charge to residents, with no deductibles. Claims are verified by Aves Argentinas, with support from Ministry of Ecology park rangers. Once an incident is confirmed, affected farmers receive compensation via a digital wallet or bank account. A support plan is also activated to help improve livestock protection and prevent future incidents. The initiative includes regular visits to assist producers in strengthening security measures and promotes broader adoption of these practices across local communities.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature, Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		UNDP Argentina, Government of the Province of Misiones, Río Uruguay Seguros, Aves Argentinas, insurers, conservation partners		Article · Detailed Case Study	

3.1.5 Habitat Banks Insurance					
PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Design Phase	Colombia	2026 – TBD	Terrestrial	Parametric/Index	Public Sector, Private Investors
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature		Private		Performance and Delivery Risk; Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Design of parametric insurance solutions to protect investments in habitat banks. The insurance product protects against key environmental risks, such as human-wildlife conflict, rainfall anomalies, and wildfires, offering confidence to investors and project developers. By reducing uncertainty and securing biodiversity assets, the insurance strengthens habitat banks, supports ecosystem resilience, and promotes greater public-private investment in nature-based solutions.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		UNDP IRFF, BIOFIN, national partners, insurers (TBD)		Article · Report	

3.1.6 Developing Insurance Products for Surf Ecosystems and Surf Breaks

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	El Salvador	2024 – 2026	Marine	Parametric/Index	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance of natural assets		Public-Private-Partnership		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems; Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Save The Waves is developing a parametric insurance product to insure and protect surf ecosystems and their associated tourism value. Save The Waves is safeguarding surf ecosystems from the impacts of erosion and extreme weather events due to climate change. This is being undertaken through a combination of securing protected area status for surf locations, stewardship and community activism.</p> <p>Through the second cycle of the Ocean Resilience Innovation Challenge, ORRAA supported Save The Waves to develop the initial concept. With support from the Government of Canada, Save The Waves is now developing a parametric insurance product and a surf ecosystem resilience trust fund in El Salvador to compensate coastal communities for revenue loss caused by the destructive nature of storms.</p> <p>This project was supported by ORRAA. This project was undertaken with the financial support of the Government of Canada through the Federal Department of Environment and Climate Change. Ce projet a été réalisé avec l'appui financier du gouvernement du Canada agissant par l'entremise du ministère fédéral de l'Environnement et du Changement climatique.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature, Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		Save The Waves		Detailed Case Study	

3.1.7 Marine Protected Area Insurance Policy

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Philippines	2023 – Ongoing	Marine	Parametric/Index	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance of natural assets		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>AXA Climate, Howden, and Blue Alliance Marine Protected Areas partnered in 2023 to develop a parametric business interruption insurance product protecting Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) that manage vulnerable coral reef ecosystems. The product triggers compensation within days of a cyclone passing within a 50km radius, based on meteorological data from government agencies. Payouts fund debris cleanup, coral restoration, repair of MPA equipment and assets such as vessels and ranger facilities, and reimburse operating losses from reef-positive businesses including ecotourism and community-based aquaculture. The programme initially covered two sites: the Turneffe Atoll in Belize (132,000 hectares, 1,000+ fishers) and North Oriental Mindoro in the Philippines (90,000 hectares, 12,000+ fishers), with Howden financing the first year's premiums. In October 2024, the coverage was renewed for 88 MPAs in the Philippines. Blue Alliance has also launched an impact loan facility backed by this insurance, offering early-stage financing to businesses committed to coral reef preservation and restoration.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		AXA Climate, Blue Marine Alliance, Howden		Article · Factsheet	

3.1.8 San Crisanto Mangrove Forest Resilience Insurance

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Mexico	2023 – Ongoing	Marine	Parametric/Index	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance of natural assets		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems; Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>AXA Climate, AXA Seguros Mexico, and ClimateSeed developed the first parametric insurance policy for the protection of mangrove forests in Mexico, covering the San Crisanto mangrove conservation and restoration project in the Yucatán Peninsula. San Crisanto is a community of approximately 150 Mayan families whose economic activity is structured around 800 hectares of mangrove forest through restoration, conservation, carbon credit sales, and ecotourism. The community is highly vulnerable to hurricanes: in 2002, Hurricane Isidore destroyed 99% of the area's mangroves. The parametric product triggers a payout of up to \$100,000 when a hurricane passes through the insured area, with the amount varying by wind strength and proximity to the core protected area. Compensation is paid directly to the policyholder, the Ejido San Crisanto community, to support mangrove regeneration, debris cleanup, and repair of fishing and ecotourism infrastructure. The insurance premium is paid by the community through funds received from annual carbon credit sales under the Voluntary Carbon Market, creating a self-sustaining financial model. The policy has been renewed three times since its launch in 2023. The project has captured approximately 47,908 tonnes of CO₂ across four reporting periods. Mangroves also reduce the impact of coastal flooding and support biodiversity-rich ecosystems, protecting and providing for local communities.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature, Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		AXA Climate, Seguros Mexico, ClimateSeed		Article · Website	

3.1.9 Coral Reef Insurance Policy — Hawai'i

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	United States	2022 – Ongoing	Marine	Parametric/Index	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance of natural assets		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems; Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Hawai'i's new policy covers all reefs across the main Hawaiian islands, covering an area of 314,976 square miles. It covers both hurricanes and tropical storms given the latter's frequency in Hawai'i. The maximum payout total is \$2 million over the year-long policy period, and \$1 million per storm, underwritten and provided by Munich Re. The minimum payout has doubled to \$200,000, an amount that enables a more meaningful post-storm response. The policy is triggered when tropical storm winds of 50 knots or greater occur in the core of the coverage area. In the event of a storm, the predetermined disbursed amount is distributed with advice from TNC as well as the Division of Aquatic Resources to enable quick damage assessment and repair.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature. Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		The Nature Conservancy, WTW, Munich Re Group		Article (1) · Article (2) · Article (3)	

3.1.10 Ping An P&C - Kelp/Seaweed

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Pilot Phase	China	2023 – Ongoing	Marine	Parametric/Index	Private - Real Economy, Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance of natural assets		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Ping An Property & Casualty Insurance has launched its first ocean carbon sink index insurance policy in Dalian, providing RMB 400,000 in carbon sink risk protection for 8866.67 square metres of kelp, shellfish, and algae. This follows the company's 2021 pilot of forest carbon sink remote sensing index insurance and expands coverage across terrestrial and marine ecosystems including forests, mangroves, and grasslands.</p> <p>The insurance provides compensation when environmental changes damage marine species and weaken carbon sink capacity, with funds directed toward post-disaster species rescue, ecological restoration, and carbon sink resource recovery. The product also enables carbon sink indicators of marine aquaculture to be listed and traded, increasing fishermen's income by converting marine carbon sinks from resources into tradeable assets.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		Ping An P&C		Article	

3.1.11 Nature Restoration & Conservation Insurance Initiative

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Global	2022 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Land Managers
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for conservation, restoration and NbS delivery, implementation, performance and management		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>SCOR's Nature Restoration and Conservation Insurance Initiative offers innovative reinsurance solutions supporting nature-resilient projects that address climate change, food and water security, and sustainable agriculture. The flagship Ecological Restoration Insurance Solution aims to bridge financing gaps for restoration projects by de-risking investment opportunities for public and private stakeholders.</p> <p>The solution comprises three products aligned with ecosystem recovery stages: "Restore" for initial recovery implementation, "Manage" for ongoing maintenance, and "Conserve" (forthcoming) for long-term integrity preservation. Developed in collaboration with the Society for Ecological Restoration, the initiative employs a standards-based due diligence process requiring projects to achieve a minimum "A" grade to qualify for coverage across diverse terrestrial biomes.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature		SCOR, Society for Ecological Restoration		Insurer Webpage · Product Factsheet · Product Illustrative Cases	

3.1.12 GaiaSicura Ltd.					
PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Global	2025 – Ongoing	Terrestrial, Marine	Hybrid	Private Investors, Private - Real Economy, Public Sector
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for conservation, restoration and NbS delivery, implementation, performance and management, Insurance to de-risk/enable investment in nature, Insurance for new and emerging business models, technologies and solutions		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems, Performance and Delivery Risk, Liability and Policy Risk	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>GaiaSicura is a UK-based licensed insurance broker specialising in bespoke insurance solutions for nature regeneration projects. The company works with specialist insurance markets to develop risk transfer mechanisms across the full lifecycle of nature projects, from design through establishment, offtake, and maintenance. Services span four client categories: project developers receive risk assessments, contract reviews, and comprehensive wrap-up insurance programmes; investors and credit buyers access coverage for non-delivery, counterparty risk, credit cancellation, buffer depletion, political risk, and green finance guarantees; third-party experts obtain professional indemnity insurance for errors and omissions; and nature-based solutions advisory services assist those seeking to utilise nature restoration for risk mitigation purposes such as flood control through beavers or coastal protection through mangroves.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature, Nature-related transition risks to people, business and the economy		GaiaSicura, Lloyd’s		Insurer Webpage	

3.1.13 Community-led Mangrove Restoration through Green Life Insurance (Seguro de Vida Verde)

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	El Salvador	2019 – Ongoing	Marine	Indemnity	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance to reduce risks to ecosystems and species		Private		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Davivienda Seguros El Salvador's Green Life Insurance (Seguro de Vida Verde) channels a part of each policy premium into community-led mangrove restoration at the Barra de Santiago Ramsar site, an 11,500-hectare protected area that has lost 60% of its mangroves over the past 50 years. Working with FUNDEMAS and GIZ, the programme funds the local women's association AMBAS and surrounding communities to restore degraded mangrove forest. To date, 8 hectares have been restored and 26,200 mangroves planted, sequestering an estimated 1,892 tonnes of CO₂ and providing paid employment to 70 families (60% women). The restored mangroves function as nature-based coastal defences, buffering storm surge, erosion and flooding, while also supporting fisheries, water purification and local livelihoods. The product has been operational for over 12 years, with the mangrove-specific focus at Barra de Santiago running since approximately 2019. In 2025, Davivienda extended the model with a collective SME version of the product.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Risks to Nature, Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		Davivienda Seguros El Salvador, FUNDEMAS, GIZ, Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (MARN), Asociación de Mujeres de la Barra de Santiago (AMBAS)		Article (1) · Article (2) · Article (3)	

3.2 Resilience Insurance

This category covers insurance for human assets and activities where nature plays a role in reducing physical risk, sometimes referred to as "nature for insurance." It includes products that reward investment in nature-based solutions through reduced premiums, schemes where communities benefit from ecosystem-based risk reduction, and coverage that responds when nature-based defences fail or underperform. Examples range from flood insurance premium discounts for communities that preserve floodplain open space to parametric products that pay out to coastal fishers when adverse weather prevents them from working.

The types of products which fall within this category are as follows:

3.2 Resilience Insurance - Product types (adapted from UNEP FI)	
→	Insurance with payouts for build back greener and more resilient
→	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
→	Insurance approaches using NbS to improve the availability and affordability of insurance

Section 3.2 Navigation Table — Resilience Insurance

Insurance solutions that integrate nature-based approaches to risk reduction by reflecting the protective value of ecosystems in premium pricing or underwriting decisions. This also includes insurance that uses NbS to improve the availability or affordability of coverage, aid post-disaster recovery, or address emerging nature-related risks.

REF	NAME	COUNTRY	REALM	TRIGGER TYPE	PRODUCT TYPE
3.2.1	California Wildfire Insurance — TNC, WTW (2025)	United States	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
3.2.2	US NFIP Community Rating System — FEMA (1990)	United States	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
3.2.3	Illinois Cover Crop Premium Discount — Illinois Dept. of Agriculture (2025)	United States	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
3.2.4	Community Insurance for Controlled Flooding — CMCC (2024)	Italy	Terrestrial	Parametric /Index	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
3.2.5	COAST Parametric Microinsurance — CCRIF SPC, CRFM (2019)	Latin America & Caribbean	Marine	Parametric /Index	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation

3.2.6	Forest Keeper Reforestation Endorsement — Mitsui Sumitomo, MS&AD (2022)	Japan	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation
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Please note, the case studies highlighted in this document represent a curated subset of the full collection of nature-related insurance products. To view all cases, please visit the [NATURANCE digital library](#).

3.2.1 California Wildfire Insurance

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	United States	2025 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Local Communities
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation		Private		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>The Nature Conservancy and WTW have launched a first-of-its-kind wildfire resilience insurance policy that accounts for forest fire mitigation efforts, structured for Tahoe Donner Association in Truckee, California. The \$2.5 million coverage, developed in collaboration with UC Berkeley's Center for Law, Energy and the Environment, demonstrates that ecological forest practices such as tree thinning and prescribed burns can reduce insurance costs. The policy covering 1,345 acres of forested and recreation land achieved a 39% lower premium and 89% lower deductible compared to properties without nature-based forest management. Globe Underwriting provided empirical analysis supporting the risk reduction assessment, offering a model for addressing California's insurance crisis amid widespread policy non-renewals.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		The Nature Conservancy, WTW, Globe Underwriting, Tahoe Donner Association, UC Berkeley		Article	

3.2.2 US National Flood Insurance Program's Community Rating System

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	United States	1990 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Local Communities, Public Sector
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation		Public		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>FEMA's Community Rating System (CRS) is a voluntary incentive programme that recognises and rewards community floodplain management practices exceeding the minimum requirements of the National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP). Over 1,500 communities participate nationwide, earning flood insurance premium discounts of 5% to 45% based on credit points for activities across four categories: public information, mapping and regulations, flood damage reduction, and flood preparedness.</p> <p>Critically, the CRS awards substantial credit points for open space preservation (Activity 420), where communities preserve floodplains as natural areas free from development. Preserving floodplain open space allows ecosystems to perform natural functions including storing floodwaters, providing habitat, and reducing flood risk. Communities can earn up to nearly 2,000 points for open space preservation alone, with additional credits for deed-restricted parcels, natural shoreline protection, wetland habitat preservation, and low-density zoning in floodplains. This creates a direct financial incentive linking nature-based solutions to reduced insurance costs for property owners.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		FEMA, state floodplain management agencies, local community governments		Factsheet · Manual	

3.2.3 Illinois Cover Crop Premium Discount Program (Fall Covers for Spring Savings)

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	United States	2019 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Private - Real Economy
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation		Public		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>The Illinois Department of Agriculture Cover Crop Premium Discount Program promotes additional acres of cover crops not covered by other state and federal program incentives. Eligible applicants receive a premium discount up to \$5 per acre on the following year's crop insurance for every cover crop acre enrolled and verified in the program. The inaugural season resulted in an additional 50,000 acres of cover crops planted, with 70% of applicants identified as planting cover crops for the first time.</p> <p>The 2025-2026 program will fund up to 190,000 acres, with 40,000 acres funded by the Illinois Environmental Protection Agency via Gulf Hypoxia Funding. Illinois is one of the leading contributors to the Gulf of Mexico's dead zone, a barren area of around 4,500 square miles deadly to fish, shrimp and other marine life. The Illinois Nutrient Loss Reduction Strategy recognises cover crops as one of the most effective in-field management strategies to stem the loss of nitrate-nitrogen and total phosphorus from corn-soybean fields.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		American Farmland Trust, Illinois Corn Growers, Illinois Stewardship Alliance, the Association of Soil & Water Conservation Districts, The Nature Conservancy, Delta Institute, Prairie Rivers Network, the Izaak Walton League, Illinois Environmental Council, the Illinois Department of Agriculture, USDA's Risk Management Agency		Government Website	

3.2.4 CMCC - Community Insurance for Controlled Flooding

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Concept Phase	Po River basin, Italy	2024 – 2026	Terrestrial	Parametric/Index	Local Communities, Public Sector
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation		Public-Private-Partnership		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>The NATURANCE Innovation Lab led by CMCC designed a community-based parametric insurance product to support controlled flooding operations by water boards in Northern Italy's Po River basin. The product would cover costs and liabilities incurred when water boards deliberately flood upstream rural land to protect downstream urban areas from more severe uncontrolled flooding.</p> <p>Premiums would be financed through a proportional tribute collected from downstream beneficiaries based on existing classification plans. Land designated for controlled flooding would be converted to nature-based solutions, enhancing flood risk reduction and generating co-benefits. Next steps include additional stakeholder workshops, international applicability testing through Network Nature Labs funding, and potential pilot applications linked to reconstruction efforts in Emilia-Romagna.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		CMCC, Aarhus University, International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), Global Infrastructure Basel Foundation (GIB-Foundation), Po River Basin District Authority (ADBPO), ANBI Veneto, ANBI Emilia-Romagna, ANBI Lombardia, Regione Lombardia, Assicurazioni Generali, Banca d'Italia, IVASS		Scorecard	

3.2.5 Caribbean Oceans and Aquaculture Sustainability Facility (COAST)

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Latin America & Caribbean	2019 – Ongoing	Marine	Parametric/Index	Local Communities, Private - Real Economy
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation		Public-Private-Partnership		Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>The Caribbean Oceans and Aquaculture Sustainability Facility (COAST) is a parametric microinsurance product developed by CCRIF SPC in partnership with the Caribbean Regional Fisheries Mechanism (CRFM), providing rapid payouts to fisherfolk and aquaculture operators in CRFM Member States following tropical cyclones and excess rainfall events. The product complements CCRIF's existing sovereign parametric insurance suite by extending coverage to livelihoods directly dependent on marine and coastal ecosystems. Payouts are triggered when weather parameters exceed predefined thresholds, enabling fishing communities to recover quickly and reduce pressure on marine resources during post-disaster periods when overfishing and unsustainable practices are most likely. By linking insurance to climate-resilient fishing, fish farming, and resource management practices, COAST promotes the sustainable use of marine and aquatic ecosystems while building financial resilience among vulnerable coastal populations. The product supports the Caribbean Community Common Fisheries Policy's Protocol on Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Management, which aims to ensure regional fisheries and aquaculture sectors are resilient to climate change and ocean acidification.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		CCRIF SPC, Caribbean Regional Fisheries Mechanism (CRFM), World Bank, US State Department		Report • Brochure • Brochure (2)	

3.2.6 Forest Keeper - Reforestation Expenses Endorsement

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Japan	2022 – Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Private - Real Economy
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for solutions integrating, incentivising or enabling nature-related risk reduction and mitigation;		Private		Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems; Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	
DESCRIPTION					
Mitsui Sumitomo Insurance (MS&AD Group) launched "Forest Keeper" in 2022 as the fourth product in its series contributing to natural capital and biodiversity conservation. The product is an endorsement attached to comprehensive corporate property insurance for forestry operators, covering reforestation expenses following forest fire: costs that were previously excluded from the company's conventional forest fire insurance. Covered expenses include site preparation, seedlings, planting, undergrowth clearing, installation of wildlife protection fencing, road network maintenance for reforestation access, and debris removal. The product is explicitly framed by MS&AD as addressing the challenge that unafforested burnt forests increase downstream landslide risk, positioning reforestation as a nature-based risk reduction measure. Payouts cover actual costs net of any government subsidies. The product forms part of MS&AD's broader "Green Resilience" strategy integrating nature-based solutions into insurance.					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related physical risk to people, business and the economy		Mitsui Sumitomo Insurance (MS&AD Insurance Group)		Report · Website · News Release (Japanese)	

3.3 Transition Insurance

This category addresses risks that arise when businesses or individuals shift toward practices that produce nature-positive outcomes or those that reduce pressures on nature. It includes products that support companies navigating changes in regulation, supply chains or land use, as well as coverage for the operational uncertainties that come with adopting new sustainable approaches. Transition Insurance remains the most emergent of the three categories, with few documented cases to date, reflecting both the novelty of the concept and the difficulty of pricing risks.

The types of products which fall within this category are as follows:

3.3 Transition Insurance - Product types (adapted from UNEP FI)	
→	Insurance for risks arising from the transition of existing activities and value chains to align with nature-positive outcomes
→	Insurance for new and emerging business models, technologies and solutions
→	Promoting practices to avoid or reduce pressures on nature through underwriting guidelines, criteria, conditions or the claims process
→	Insurance risk pooling mechanisms to support the implementation and scaling of transition pathways

Section 3.3 Navigation Table — Transition Insurance

Insurance solutions which cover risks arising when businesses change their activities, operations or supply chains to reduce pressures on nature or achieve nature-positive outcomes.

REF	NAME	COUNTRY	REALM	TRIGGER TYPE	PRODUCT TYPE
3.3.1	Insurance for Carbon Credit Forwards — Swiss Re, Good Carbon (2024)	Global	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for risks arising from transition to nature-positive outcomes
3.3.2	Environmental Risk Biodiversity Deductible Reduction — AXA XL, Marsh France (2021)	France	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Insurance for risks arising from transition to nature-positive outcomes

Please note, the case studies highlighted in this document represent a curated subset of the full collection of nature-related insurance products. To view all cases, please visit the NATURANCE [digital library](#).

3.3.1 Insurance for carbon credit forwards²

PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	Global	2024 - Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Private - Real Economy
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for risks arising from the transition of existing activities and value chains to align with nature-positive outcomes		Private		Performance and Delivery Risk	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>Insurance for long-term carbon credit purchases that offers in-kind replacements in case of defaults of carbon credit sellers. A solution that helps companies secure their future carbon credit supply by insuring the provision of global carbon credits from afforestation, reforestation and revegetation projects with delivery dates up to five years in the future. The insurance of non-delivery due to natural catastrophes, weather events, and certain political risks aims to enhance confidence for carbon credit buyers in the purchase of credits on a forward contract basis and attract more private investment in nature-based climate solutions especially where there is a lag between investment and experiencing benefits.</p> <p>Furthermore, by strengthening the financial trust in carbon credits acquired on a forward contract basis, the product allows the transition of activities in adopting nature-positive carbon mitigation approaches that otherwise may have been deemed as too risky.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related transition risk to people, business and the economy		SwissRE, Good Carbon		Article	

² Carbon credits insurance is an emerging product type with many insuring against non-delivery of credits. It is included here as being a relevant nature-related insurance product as it addresses a driver of nature change. Refer to the [digital library](#) for further examples of carbon credit insurance projects.

3.3.2 AXA XL - Environmental Risk Biodiversity Deductible Reduction					
PROJECT MATURITY	COUNTRY / REGION	START / END YEAR	REALM	INSURANCE TRIGGER TYPE	INSURANCE SCHEME TARGET
Active	France	2021 - Ongoing	Terrestrial	Indemnity	Private - Real Economy
INSURANCE PRODUCT TYPE		INSURANCE PROVIDER / SCHEME DEVELOPERS		INSURED RISK	
Insurance for risks arising from the transition of existing activities and value chains to align with nature-positive outcomes		Private		Liability and Policy Risk	
DESCRIPTION					
<p>In France, a 2016 biodiversity law introduced obligations for companies to restore damaged natural sites to baseline conditions following environmental accidents. In response, AXA XL developed an underwriting incentive within its Environmental Risk insurance policies: corporate clients that (i) commission an independent ecological assessment of nearby natural areas to establish a biodiversity baseline, and (ii) integrate the findings into their accident prevention and management plans, receive a 25% reduction in their policy deductibles. This mechanism encourages proactive biodiversity risk management by embedding nature-related criteria directly into insurance terms, improving clients' preparedness for ecological restoration obligations while rewarding preventive action. Marsh France brokered the development of this provision. The initiative was developed with input from ACT4Nature, an alliance of French companies, academic bodies and public institutions.</p>					
BROADER RISK ADDRESSED		PARTNERS		SOURCES	
Nature-related transition risk to people, business and the economy		AXA XL, ACT4Nature, Marsh France		Article • Report	

4. Analysis of Nature-related Insurance Products Identified in Compendium

This section analyses the full set of 47 entries in the compendium [digital library](#) to identify patterns, gaps and emerging trends across nature-related insurance products. The digital library aims to capture products for which sufficient public documentation was available at the time of writing. It should be considered as a snapshot and not a complete market overview. The 21 case studies presented in [Section 3](#) are a subset of this wider collection. **The below analysis refers to the full digital library rather than the subset presented in this report.**

4.1 Patterns Across the Digital Library

Nature-related Insurance Products by Start Year

N = 43, 4 products with unknown start years excluded

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.1.1: Distribution of Digital Library Entries by First Year of Operation/Pilot

The majority of schemes in the digital library have been established within the last eight years, with seven schemes launched in 2024 and eight in 2025. This indicates an increasing trend in both the use of insurance products to address risks to nature and the recognition of nature’s risk reduction capabilities by the insurance sector. The oldest scheme in the compendium is the US National Flood Insurance Program’s (NFIP) Community Rating System (CRS), which was founded in 1990. While the scheme did not explicitly position itself as nature-positive, it has consistently recognised and awarded nature-based approaches through open-space preservation since the founding of the CRS scheme in 1990 and expanded the range of premium discount-eligible nature-positive activities with every new Coordinator’s Manual release (FEMA, 2021).

Overall, digital library entries seem to fall into one of two modalities of insurance: the creation of purpose-built products, and the adaptation of existing ones to nature-related issues. While most solutions appear to be purpose-built products addressing nature risks, two schemes stand out as examples of how schemes can adapt to nature-related risks and needs. The NFIP case study was built to primarily address flood risk to properties across the US. However through the adoption of the Community Rating System which includes open-space preservation as an eligible nature-based intervention for flood insurance premium discounts, the insurance product recognises nature-

related approaches as a method of risk reduction (FEMA, 2021). Similarly, AXA’s Environmental Liability Insurance caters to mergers and acquisitions (M&A) transactions primarily, but includes a 25% discount in response to new French regulations, encouraging firms to conduct environmental assessments and avoid risks to nature or personnel by updating their safety and management protocols (France Assureurs, 2025). This demonstrates that there are a variety of design mechanisms for insurance products to consider nature-related issues.

Nature-related Insurance Products by Project Maturity

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.1.2: Distribution of Digital Library Entries by Maturity

The library predominantly consists of active (beyond pilot stage) projects (~81% of all entries), with just 19% in the pilot, design or concept phase. This distribution could signal that nature-related insurance products are commercially viable, with evidence indicating that insurance products have successfully moved beyond an experimental phase and have demonstrated sufficient viability to sustain commercial or institutional operation. However the relatively small share of early-stage schemes may not necessarily reflect the maturity of insurance products as it may be due to evidence of many early-stage schemes being unpublished.

For investors and policymakers seeking proven frameworks to replicate or scale, the evidence base offers a meaningful starting point. For those interested in enabling or investing in insurance solutions for nature, the pilot-stage cases represent areas where further support could accelerate

the transition to viability, whether in the form of concessional capital, regulatory enabling conditions, or technical assistance.

Figure 4.1.3: Geographic Spread of Digital Library Entries

The case studies cover a range of regions, with the majority being emerging markets.

The Asia-Pacific region had the largest number of cases, accounting for 23% of all digital library entries of which China and Japan combined accounted for half. Around 27% of cases in the Asia-Pacific region were in the pilot phase indicating there is a significant degree of product development in the region. Notably, many of the solutions were designed to benefit smallholders in primary/nature-intensive sectors such as cattle rearing, fishing and agriculture with another large share of solutions focussed on insuring natural capital for their carbon-sink capacities.

Latin America & the Caribbean contained 11 out of 47 (~23%) digital library entries spread out across the region. Notably there were a number of reef insurance products serving the Caribbean region given their role in reducing the impacts of hurricanes as well as emerging solutions around marine-adjacent habitats such as mangroves. Unlike Asia-Pacific, the majority of products identified in Latin America & the Caribbean were active, with just two in the design phase. Both of the design phase products were terrestrial in focus, possibly indicating that nature-related insurance products addressing risks in marine/coastal areas are a more mature/developed market in the region relative to terrestrial insurance products (see [Section 4.1.4](#) for further information).

Within the global North, North America was the most represented region accounting for 19% of cases in the digital library. Notably, all products were found within the United States and were active. Out of the nine schemes, two were entirely run by the public sector (the National Flood Insurance Programme and the Illinois State Cover Crop Premium Discount) and two were products catering to government-mandated ecosystem restoration, indicating the enabling role that the public sector could play in the region.

Sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 3 of 47 entries in the digital library. Notably, none of the products directly insured natural assets; instead, the insured risks were political, delivery, performance, and sovereign credit risks, with nature-positive elements integrated into the product design. While all the products in the region are active, this does not necessarily indicate a lack of innovation or experimentation with newer products and models as we have identified semi-formalised proposals for insurance addressing human-wildlife conflict in the region.

The digital library contains four entries from Europe. All solutions focussed on the terrestrial realm and two were developed in response to the introduction of nature-positive regulations such as BNG in England or The French Biodiversity Law (Environmental Act, 2021; Ministry of European and Foreign Affairs, 2020). The only concept phase product listed originates from the NATURANCE project, focusing on an innovative insurance design using NbS and controlled flooding in the Po River basin. More details on the design and its development can be accessed via the [Innovation Lab report](#) (Marin et al., 2025).

Finally, 8 of 47 digital library entries (representing roughly 1/6th of all products) were of global scope, indicating that insurance products need not be restricted to specific regions. Of these global products 63% are for carbon credits addressing either delivery/performance risks, political risks or risks to the underlying natural asset. A further 25% of products support nature restoration and long-term management with highly bespoke covers.

Nature-related Insurance Products by IUCN Realm

(Products may address multiple realms)

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.1.4: Realm Addressed by Digital Library Entries

A narrow majority of 57% of insurance products addressed nature-related risks in the terrestrial realm, which could indicate that terrestrial nature-related insurance products are the most advanced and widespread. Around 40% of products addressed risks in the marine realm and only 4% of products addressed risks in the freshwater realm. Amongst terrestrial solutions, 85% of products were active or have been completed and around 15% were in the concept, design or pilot phases. These ratios largely correspond with that of the total digital library (see Figure 4.1.2). Amongst marine products, 78% were in the active phase and the remaining 22% were either in the concept, design or pilot phase with a particularly high concentration in the Latin America & Caribbean region. A significant portion of products insuring freshwater or terrestrial ecosystems/activities do indirectly influence ecological and socio-economic outcomes in marine areas, for example, by incentivising reduced fertiliser use inland which otherwise would wash into marine environments. Of the two products in the freshwater realm, both were active solutions operating in the USA.

4.2 Insurance Product Design Analysis

Each entry in the digital library was tagged with a set of insurance-specific fields covering trigger type, partnership structure, spatial scale and product type. This section analyses the distribution of products across these fields to identify patterns in how nature-related insurance products are structured and where gaps in design and coverage remain. Definitions for all fields and their values are provided in [Annex B](#).

Nature-related Insurance Products by Trigger Type

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.2.1: Digital Library Entries by Trigger Type

The majority (~60%) of all digital library entries consisted of products using indemnity-based triggers, with parametric triggers accounting for 34% of entries. Only one product used hybrid triggers which was released only in 2025 and is therefore very recent. Two entries did not have a clear indication of what trigger was used and were therefore classified as ‘unknown’.

Nature-related Insurance Products by Start Year and Trigger Type

N = 41, 6 products with unknown start year or trigger type excluded

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

■ Parametric / Index ■ Hybrid ■ Indemnity

Figure 4.2.2: Digital Library Entries by Trigger Type and Start Year

Parametric products were only present in case studies identified from 2022 onwards, reflecting their status as a recent and novel product design. The noticeable spike in the proportion of parametric insurance in 2023 and 2024 can be linked to the launch of multiple parametric coral reef insurance schemes as well as parametric carbon credit insurance schemes in succession. Notably, both products that launched in 2026 intend to use parametric triggers but are still in their design phase.

Indemnity models are used in a range of cases including but not limited to property insurance (such as the NFIP), carbon credit insurance, political risk insurance applied at a sovereign level and schemes offering protection for habitats. A notable insight is that indemnity-based insurance products addressing political and sovereign credit risks were found to usually involve a public sector financial backer such as the Development Finance Corporation in the U.S. or the Foreign and Commonwealth Development Office in the UK. Fully private political risk insurance using indemnity credits only catered to carbon credits, particularly addressing changes in national regulations or political risks that slowdown the sale/export of carbon credits (Kita Earth, n.d.; Araullo, 2024).

Parametric solutions were the next most common modality of insurance trigger type. Parametric solutions were notably more recently founded with 69% of parametric insurance entries having start dates within the past three years. Of the 16 parametric products, 6 of them were early stage

schemes either being a concept, designed or piloted. This aligns with broader findings around parametric insurance designs being a more novel trend in insurance (Bonazzi et al., 2024; Glinskis & Murphy, 2025). Finally, the vast majority of parametric insurance entries in the digital library were based in the Global South, mainly in Latin America & the Caribbean and Asia-Pacific regions.

The only hybrid trigger product in the digital library was launched in 2025 and meant to cater to both terrestrial and marine ecosystems. This indicates that this is a relatively recent innovation that has entered the market.

Nature-related Insurance Products by Insurance Scheme Developer

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.2.3: Digital Library Entries by Partnership Structure

Private sector actors account for the majority of case studies (62%), with public-private partnerships representing 34%, and fully public models making up only 4% of the library (consisting of two entries). The prevalence of private models could partly reflect that (re)insurance is primarily provided by private sector players. It also may signal that a genuine commercial appetite for nature-based insurance exists and that these are not always purely donor-driven or policy-mandated products. The 34% share of public-private-partnership models speaks to the complexity of nature-risks necessitating cross-stakeholder collaboration. In these arrangements, the private sector typically acts as the (re)insurer, while the public sector plays a range of complementary roles expanded upon below:

1. Coordinator of the scheme's design and governance: To demonstrate the government of Ecuador and the Development Finance Corporation backed by the American Government have codesigned a marine conservation-linked bond out of refinanced debt linked with political risk insurance to divert funds towards conservation in the Galapagos Islands that otherwise would have been used to service Ecuador's debt (DFC, 2023a);
2. Backstop against tail risks or subsidisation of programme costs that would otherwise make private participation unviable: The popularly cited MAR Fund Insurance for Mesoamerican coral reefs received premium financing from the German government via KfW ensuring it remains affordable and enabling the participation of private insurers (Wharton, 2024); and
3. Purchasing entity acquiring cover on behalf of communities that may not afford it individually or to pool risks across a community: Government as insurance buyer, allows insurance coverage to reach beneficiaries who would otherwise be excluded from the market due to higher premiums as proposed by the concept put forth by the CMCC applied at a river basin level or for livestock losses in Comandante Andresito (Martin et al., 2025; IRFF, 2025).

Fully public insurance models are uncommon amongst the digital library entries, with only two cases identified, both of which were in the US. The first scheme is the NFIP (property flood insurance) coordinated and run by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and the second is a state-level cover crop premium discount scheme run by the Illinois Department of Agriculture (FEMA, 2025; Kousky & Burley, 2025).

Nature-related Insurance Products by Geographic Scale

(Products may operate at multiple scales; percentages do not sum to 100%)

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.2.4: Digital Library Entries by Spatial Scale of Solution

Insurance solutions within the digital library spanned a range of spatial scales in terms of their scope of insured risks. 57% of all insurance products were applied at a local level with a further 36% at the sub-national level. Finally 19% of solutions were at the national scale and 9% at a multi-national scale. Overall, 23% of products operated across more than one spatial scale.³

Of local level solutions, project-level solutions for carbon credits, nature credits or ecosystem restoration were well represented with cases both across the global South and global North. Most notably, many of the carbon credit schemes were either located in the global South or were globally available products, whereas insurance for nature credits such as BNG or ecosystem restoration schemes were only located in the global North. One possible driving factor behind this could be the presence of regulations that mandate ecosystem restoration or nature-positive outcomes such as Biodiversity Net Gain in the UK or Mitigation Banks in the US (USEPA, 2025; Environment Act, 2021).

Sub-national solutions were the second most commonly represented category and were diverse in terms of their spatial sub-scale of operation. A few different modes of operations could be observed amongst the entries expanded on below:

³ Percentages will not add up to 100% as a single product may operate across more than one spatial scale

1. Insurance purchased at the sub-national level, payments are made subnationally: In some cases the insurance was purchased by a sub-national entity such as a state, province or municipality to insurer a natural asset (e.g. coral reefs) or a nature-positive intervention of some kind as seen with reef insurance for all of Hawai'i (TNC, 2022).
2. Insurance was purchased at the sub-national level, payments disbursed locally: In certain examples insurance was still purchased sub-nationally such as against flood risks or against cattle losses against jaguar attacks (IRFF, 2025). Sub-national insurance need not be limited to a single municipality, as observed with the CMCC flood insurance which is applied across the entire Po River basin consisting of multiple municipalities/households (Martin et al., 2025).
3. Insurance product's geographic scope is restricted at a sub-national level: In some cases, while the purchasers of the insurance could be individuals, businesses or local organisations the product is only available within a certain region for example insurance for grasslands in Inner Mongolia (Munich Re, 2022).

There were a number of products at the national level which could also be further grouped based on either the risk being insured, the purchaser of the insurance or the way risk is pooled:

1. Insurance provided or purchased at national level: Most of the digital library entries that fall under this grouping were for political or sovereign credit risk linked to conservation outcomes such as those seen in Ecuador, Gabon and Belize (DFC, 2023a; DFC, 2023b; Fontana-Raina & Grund, 2022).
2. Risk insured is at national level: In many of the other cases, the risk insured involves a nationally managed entity or insured against political risks which are dictated by national policies. One such example is insurance for marine protected areas in the Philippines (Jimenez-Sanchez, 2024).
3. Risk pooling occurs at a national level: Finally there are some products where the end-purchaser may be a local level entity such as a project but where the risk is pooled nationally. The TerraFirm Risk Retention Group for example provides insurance to individual land trusts however, their product is available across the US and the risks are pooled nationally against litigation costs (TerraFirma, n.d.).

The least represented scale was the multi-national scale (i.e., across more than one country). Of the four products entered into the digital library, three of them had a marine focus. Two of the solutions insured coral reefs which extended across national boundaries while the latter was a micro-insurance for fisheries pooled at a multi-national level. The relatively smaller number of multi-national scale products, especially outside reef insurance, could indicate that it remains a somewhat underexplored category of insurance schemes.

Figure 4.2.5: Digital Library Entries by UNEP FI Category and Product Type

The most common product types of insurance in the library were those targeting tangible and proximate risks: products which enable/de-risk investments in nature, direct insurance of natural assets and integrating nature-based risk-reduction. The business case in these categories is relatively straightforward as there is an identifiable asset, an insurable risk, and a defined beneficiary which makes product design and pricing more traceable.

The least represented subcategories (amongst those that had examples) were insurance to remediate prior nature impacts, insurance for transition of value-chains, and insurance for new & emerging business models. In addition, four categories had no examples at all: the use of NbS to improve insurance availability/affordability, payouts to build back greener, promotion of practices to avoid/reduce pressures on nature and risk pooling to support transition pathways.

Overall, insurance for nature positive accounted for the largest proportion of products, amounting to 79% of cases followed by resilience insurance at 17% and transition insurance at just 4%. Taken together, this distribution indicates a trend of nature-related insurance products largely being developed around protecting natural assets and de-risking investment in them. An emerging frontier is one where insurance begins to address the *pressures acting on nature* such as business practices/operations and land use decisions, and supporting the transition to nature-positive outcomes. This is a complex and currently less commercially proven space. Further growth in this area rests upon businesses making clear and credible commitments to nature-positive transition and the pathways for doing so being more defined for insurers to model risks (UNEP, 2024; WWF et al., 2023; Business for Nature et al., 2026).

4.3 Policy alignment: UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Global Biodiversity Framework

To understand how nature-related insurance products contribute to broader policy objectives, each entry in the digital library was assessed for its alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Alignment was coded manually based on available documentation for each product, and should be treated as indicative rather than definitive. Where case studies were already using SDGs and GBFs to frame and align their impact assessments, we have aligned where possible.

Nature-related Insurance Products by SDG Alignment

Number of products aligned with each SDG – top 10 shown (N = 47)
 (Products may be tagged with multiple SDGs)
 Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.3.1: Digital Library Entries and their SDG Alignment

Analysis indicated that SDGs 13⁴, 14⁵, 15⁶, and 17⁷ were the most commonly addressed. SDG 13 (Climate Action) was associated with around 81% of solutions, demonstrating the close interconnections between climate and nature risks, and perhaps that insurance solutions addressing climate risks are more advanced than those addressing nature-related risks. SDG 15 (Life on Land), addressed by 62% of products was notably more prevalent than SDG 14 (Life Below Water), addressed only by half of the products, reflecting a skew toward terrestrial environments that is consistent with knowledge and action for terrestrial-related nature risks being further advanced than marine-related risks. The strong contribution towards SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) reflects a structural feature of many case studies: they tend to involve multiple stakeholders, bringing together insurers, governments, communities, and conservation actors. This is further supported by the prominence of public-private partnership models within the case studies (see [Section 4.2.2](#)).

⁴ Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts - This SDG covers a range of key outcomes including strengthening adaptive capacity to climate extremes, improving institutional/individual capacity for climate mitigation and mobilising finances for the Green Climate Fund

⁵ Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development - This SDG includes actions to reduce pollution/pressures on marine environments, ensure sustainable use of marine resources, conserve marine areas, support SIDS and provide market-access to small-scale fishers

⁶ Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss - The various actions/targets under the ambit of this SDG include conservation/restoration/sustainable management of terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems, reducing/avoiding drivers of desertification, biodiversity loss and poaching, promoting equitable sharing of nature-derived benefits, integrating nature into national accounts/local planning and mobilise financial resources for nature.

⁷ Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development - This SDG covers a range of different partnerships to unlock development with partnerships between public, private and civil society sectors and using ODA being particularly relevant to case studies

Nature-related Insurance Products by GBF Target Alignment

Number of products aligned with each GBF target — top 10 shown (N = 47)

(Products may be tagged with multiple GBF targets)

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.3.2: Digital Library Entries and their GBF Targets Alignment

The same analysis applied to the Global Biodiversity Framework targets found that most commonly addressed targets were 2⁸, 3⁹, 8¹⁰, 11¹¹, and 19¹². Overall, Target 8 which addresses the minimisation of climate and ocean acidification impacts on biodiversity was the most prominent, addressed by 64% of all cases. This echoes the general prominence given to climate change within insurance products, as seen with the SDGs (see Figure 4.3.1). The next most addressed target was Target 19, which aims to mobilise \$200 billion for nature, accounted for 60% of all products. This

⁸ Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems – This target commits to ensuring that by 2030 at least 30% of degraded terrestrial, inland water, and marine and coastal ecosystems are under restoration

⁹ Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas – Commits to conserving and managing at least 30% of terrestrial and marine areas by 2030

¹⁰ Minimise the Impacts of Climate Change on Biodiversity and Build Resilience – This target focuses on minimising the impact of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity through mitigation, adaptation and disaster risk reduction actions while minimising negative and fostering positive impacts of climate action on biodiversity.

¹¹ Restore, Maintain and Enhance Nature's Contributions to People – This target addresses the maintenance and enhancement of ecosystem functions and services through nature-based solutions and/or ecosystem-based approaches for the benefit of all people and nature.

¹² Mobilize \$200 Billion per Year for Biodiversity – This target aims to substantially increase financial resources from all sources (domestic, international, public, private) to implement national biodiversity strategies, mobilising at least \$200 billion per year by 2030. Key elements include increasing international financial flows from developed to developing countries, leveraging private finance, stimulating innovative schemes such as payment for ecosystem services, green bonds and biodiversity credits, and optimising co-benefits between biodiversity and climate finance.

highlights the role insurance can play in mobilising finance for nature at scale. The next most represented target was Target 11, centred around maximising nature’s contribution to people, amounting to 53% of all digital library entries. This demonstrates that insurers are increasingly recognising the risk-reduction role that nature can play, especially in vulnerable and exposed communities. Finally, 51% and 47% of insurance products contributed towards the restoration and conservation of nature respectively, highlighting how insurance can accelerate restoration by acting as a de-risker and conserve nature by framing it as an asset worth safeguarding.

4.4 Analysis of interaction with risk: risk reduction vs risk transfer

Nature-related Insurance Products by Insurance Mechanism

All products serve a risk transfer function; a subset also incorporate risk reduction
 Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.4.1: Digital Library Entries That Include Risk Reduction Elements

Across digital library entries, risk reduction appears to be integrated into insurance product design, or enabled through risk transfer, in a variety of ways. However, insurance schemes with a risk reduction aspect still only made up fewer than 30% of case studies reviewed. An overview of how risk reduction elements have been embedded or enabled is summarised below:

- Nesting within risk transfer structure: Where a proportion of premiums from an existing scheme is channeled towards nature-positive risk reduction as seen with El Salvador’s Seguro de Vida Verde programme (UNDRR, 2025)
- Risk transfer as a preserver of risk-reduction capacities: Where risk transfer is used to maintain natural assets and their risk reduction capacities, such as reef insurance schemes

with quick payouts post-disaster for reef restoration activities (Caribbean Biodiversity Fund, 2025; Wharton, 2024).

- Risk transfer as a de-risier of risk-reduction activities: Nature-based risk reduction activities carry risks of failure, underperformance or potential negative effects on third parties. Risk transfer could help address those risks to ensure their implementation such as with prescribed burns in forests (Cardozo, 2025).
- Risk reduction as an incentive: In some cases risk transfer solutions could introduce incentives such as premium discounts or lower deductibles in exchange for nature-based risk reduction by the entity covered. This is a common route to embed risk reduction, especially amongst existing risk transfer solutions (FEMA, 2025; FEMA, 2021; France Assureurs, 2025).

The configuration of risk reduction and risk transfer within nature-related insurance products is diverse and not yet standardised. Greater integration of risk reduction into risk transfer design is an important area of opportunity that could strengthen both the effectiveness and long-term viability of nature-related insurance products (Surminski, 2013).

Nature-related Insurance Products by Start Year and Risk Approach

N = 43, 4 products with unknown start year excluded

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

■ Risk Transfer + Risk Reduction ■ Risk Transfer Only

Figure 4.4.2: Digital Library Entries by Start Year and Risk Reduction

Overall, when focussing on the use of nature as a form of risk reduction as an active choice within insurance products, a gradual rise in their prominence is visible. The spike in the proportion of schemes in 2019 can be explained by the launch of schemes that centre the risk reduction potential of nature such as the MAR Fund, the Seguro de Vida Verde in El Salvador and the application of risk coverage for the construction of the Prince Hendrik Sand Dyke project (Wharton, 2024; UNDRR, 2025; Swiss Re, n.d.).

4.5 Analysis of interaction with risk: risk-based framework

Annex C introduces a risk-based framework for nature-based insurance products that distinguishes between the risk being insured by the product and the broader risk that the insurance solution is designed to address. Insured risk refers to the specific risk that is insured by the product or insurer. The broader risk on the other hand refers to the wider societal risk that is addressed by the product. Refer to [Annex C](#) for further details of the terms in this section.

Nature-related Insurance Products by Insured Risk

(Products may address more than one type of insurable risk)

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.5.1: Digital Library entries by Insured Risk

The most commonly *insured* risk was risk to natural assets or ecosystems, accounting for 43% of all digital library entries followed closely by physical risk to individuals, businesses and the economy amounting to around 34% of them. Performance and delivery risks relating to nature projects were insured by 21% of products respectively. The least insured risks were political & sovereign

credit risk and liability & policy risk accounting for 13% and 11% of cases respectively. Approximately 23% of digital library products insured more than one type of insured risk.¹³

Nature-related Insurance Products by Broader Risk Addressed

(Products may be tagged with multiple risk types)

Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.5.2: Digital Library Entries by Broader Risk Addressed¹⁴

When analysing *broader* risks addressed, 74% of insurance products in the digital library address risks to nature. Nature-related physical risks to people, business and the economy is the second most addressed border risk accounting for 40% of all insurance products. Finally, nature-related transition risk remains seldom addressed by products in the digital library accounting for just 6% of cases. This could reflect that transitioning towards business models with nature positive outcomes is a newer frontier for the insurance sector as well as individuals and businesses as a whole.

¹³ Percentages will not add up to 100% as a single product may insure more than one insured risk

¹⁴ Percentages will not add up to 100% as a single product may insure more than one broader risk

Insured Risks by Broader Risk Category

Number of products addressing both categories
 Source: NATURANCE Digital Library (47 products)

Figure 4.5.3: Broader Risks vs Insured Risks Addressed by Digital Library Entries

Figure 4.5.3 demonstrates that insured risks and broader nature-related risks do not map onto each other 1-to-1 as they are dependent on the context of each product design. For example, in carbon credits forward insurance, the product insures against the risk of non-delivery, however the broader risk addressed is transition risk as it makes carbon credits financially safer for organisations to purchase (Wallquist, 2025). Similarly, while the delivery of nature projects is insured by restoration bonds, the broader risk addressed is the risk to nature as it ensures that the restoration activity meets standards stipulated by regulations and enables investment (Great American Insurance Company, n.d.).

Of the case studies designed to address broader risks to nature, only 18 of 35 cases directly insure risks to natural assets and ecosystems. A significant portion of products insure other kinds of insurable risks such as physical risks (8) and performance & delivery risks (9). This indicates that many nature-related insurance products addressing broader risks to nature can do so both directly and indirectly. Similarly, of products designed to address broader physical risks, 15 of 19 did so by insuring physical risks to people and 7 insured natural assets and ecosystems. Finally, of the 3 products that addressed transition risk, 2 insured either performance and delivery risks or liability and policy risks.

During the collection process, we identified a number of cases that fit more than one category. For example, cases that addressed the broader nature-related physical risks to people, business and the economy often also address risks to nature due to having co-benefits for nature. This reflects the complexity of nature-related insurance products both in their intended benefits and means of handling risk. The full set of case studies published in the NATURANCE [digital library](#) are marked with multiple categories where applicable.

5. Conclusion

The compendium provides a single reference point for practitioners seeking to understand the current landscape of nature-related insurance. The guidance collected in [Section 2](#), drawn from the NATURANCE project and wider literature, offers entry points for readers at different levels of expertise and across different roles. The case studies in [Section 3](#) and the full digital library of 47 products provide a practical evidence base of how insurance is being applied across geographies, ecosystems and risk types. This should be seen as a snapshot and not an exhaustive market overview, as there are new products emerging regularly, as well as many pilots or innovations that are not openly published. The full set of case studies, along with additional literature and other NATURANCE deliverables, can be accessed through the NATURANCE [Digital Library](#). Together, these resources are intended to support insurers developing new products, policymakers designing enabling frameworks, and investors seeking to de-risk nature-based projects.

The analysis in [Section 4](#) confirms that meaningful innovation is underway. A range of product designs now exists, from parametric cover for coral reefs to premium discounts for ecological land management, spanning diverse trigger mechanisms, partnership structures and spatial scales. Yet persistent challenges remain. While most products remain primarily risk transfer mechanisms, there is growing recognition that combining risk transfer with risk reduction strengthens both the commercial and environmental case, though doing so adds complexity to product design.

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Annex A - NATURANCE and external guidance: summary of cross-cutting themes and findings

Why does nature loss matter for insurers?	
<p>There is growing recognition across the literature that nature loss is not an externality to the insurance business model but a direct driver of claims volatility and widens the protection gap. As ecosystems buffering against extreme weather events degrade, losses become harder to price using historical data. The guidance consistently finds that where ecosystems are intact or restored, insured losses are measurably lower, but this relationship is not yet systematically reflected in how insurers assess and price risk.</p>	
Barrier identified in the guidance	Emerging solutions and suggested steps
<p>Nature loss is widening the protection gap</p> <p>WWF (2.2.8) finds that protection gaps averaged \$64 billion per year in the US (2021–2024) and €59 billion per year in the EU (2021–2023), with deforestation increasing large-scale flood risk by up to 700%.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Geneva Association (2.2.1) and UNEP FI (2.2.4) argue that insurers need to move from reactive pricing to proactive risk management that accounts for ecosystem intactness. • Swiss Re's BES Index (2.2.6), which measures ecosystem health at one-square-kilometre resolution across ten services, provides one tool for doing so at scale, finding that 55% of global GDP depends moderately or highly on ecosystem services. • NATURANCE (2.1.14) echoes similar findings demonstrating using a DIFI model, that implementing NbS on average reduces the damages from flooding by 37% and reduce premiums for vulnerable households.
<p>Many climate losses are misclassified, obscuring the role of nature</p> <p>UNEP FI's "Rooted in Risk" (2.2.11) argues that losses conventionally classified as climate risks are often more accurately understood as nature-related physical risks stemming from degraded ecosystem services.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Invest4Nature study (2.2.7) found that river restoration in Portugal reduced flood damage to buildings by 43% using the avoided damage costs approach. • Earth Security's work in the Philippines (2.2.14) demonstrated that mangroves can reduce annual property damage by up to 30% nationally by including them as a parameter in their CAT modelling. • These findings suggest that reclassifying nature-related losses could reveal the true scale of the opportunity for risk reduction through ecosystem protection. NATURANCE asserts that this requires both recognition of nature (through legal subjectification, risk internalisation or converging on metrics) as well as improving data quality and availability (2.1.12).
Evidence from nature-related insurance products	
<p>The nature-related insurance products collected in the digital library suggest that the market is responding to this evidence. At least 9 new products were identified as launching in both 2024 and 2025, signifying year-on-year growth in the overall number of products operating at the nature-insurance intersection (Section 4.1). Approximately 81% of all entries are classified as active schemes (Section 4.2), indicating that some models have demonstrated sufficient viability to sustain commercial operation, though the relatively small share of early-stage schemes may also reflect gaps in publicly available documentation rather than market maturity alone.</p>	
Recommendations emerging from the guidance	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurers would benefit from treating ecosystem condition as a core variable in risk assessment rather than an externality, recognising that nature loss directly shapes the losses flowing through to claims. • Policymakers and regulators can support the development and adoption of standardised metrics linking ecosystem intactness/services to insured losses, helping to close the evidence gap across geographies and hazard types. • Researchers and insurers can collaborate to extend the evidence base beyond the small number of well-documented contexts where the relationship between ecosystem condition and insurance claims is currently quantified. 	

How can insurance go beyond compensating losses to reducing them?

A consistent finding across the literature is that the most effective insurance approaches at the nature-insurance intersection do not treat risk transfer in isolation but embed incentives for nature-based risk reduction within the product itself. However, the guidance also warns that where products operate in vulnerable or marginalised communities, attention to who benefits and who bears the cost is essential for both legitimacy and uptake.

Barrier identified in the guidance

Emerging solutions and suggested steps

Most insurance products transfer risk without incentivising its reduction

UNEP FI (2.2.4) and NATURANCE D4.3 (2.1.14) find that conventional insurance rarely rewards policyholders for investing in nature-based risk reduction, missing an opportunity to lower future claims.

- UNEP FI (2.2.4) and NATURANCE D4.3 (2.1.14) recommend integrating incentives into underwriting such as offering premium discounts or lower deductibles for verified nature-based risk reduction.
- findings from NATURANCE’s Innovation Lab (2.1.5) developed by WTW suggest that trigger-based financing could also catalyse recovery post-heat waves. Similarly Howden and Pollination (2.2.5) identify parametric triggers as a complementary mechanism, providing rapid post-event liquidity for time-sensitive ecosystem repair that preserves the risk-reducing capacity of natural assets. Similarly,

Products risk excluding vulnerable communities who need them most

NATURANCE D3.2 (2.1.11) and EDF (2.2.3) highlight the risk that insurers withdraw from low-income or marginalised communities deemed high-risk, and stress that solutions must be socially legitimate to achieve uptake.

- Community-based models that distribute costs equitably are advocated by NATURANCE D3.2 (2.1.11) and EDF (2.2.3).
- Co-design with affected communities is identified across NATURANCE’s Innovation Labs (2.1.6) as essential for building the trust on which uptake depends, particularly where the burdens of nature-based interventions fall on different groups from those who benefit from the risk reduction.

Evidence from nature-related insurance products

The digital library provides evidence that these principles are being put into practice. Impact underwriting is already operational, with TNC and WTW’s California wildfire policy (3.2.1) achieving a 39% lower premium for ecologically managed land and AXA XL and Marsh (3.3.2) offering a 25% deductible reduction for biodiversity baseline assessments in France. Parametric products, now a third of all entries (Section 4.2), enable rapid post-event payouts directed at ecosystem restoration, as seen in the Hawai’i coral reef (3.1.9) and Philippine MPA (3.1.7) policies. On equity, the CMCC controlled flooding scheme (3.2.4) shows how inequitable cost distribution can be addressed explicitly within product design through co-design processes. However, risk reduction is not yet universally integrated across the digital library entries (Section 4.4), with only 27% of schemes integrating risk reduction.

Recommendations emerging from the guidance

- **Insurers and product designers** can embed risk reduction incentives within the transfer mechanism itself, whether through premium discounts, funded restoration or coverage of liability risks that dissuade stakeholders from implementing nature-based interventions.
- **Insurers and scheme developers** could benefit from co-designing products with affected communities to ensure equitable distribution of costs and benefits, building the trust and encouraging uptake on which commercial viability depends.
- **Policymakers** could support the scaling of parametric trigger mechanisms that enable rapid post-event ecosystem recovery, given their growing presence.

Who needs to be involved to make nature-related insurance viable?

The literature finds that most insurance interventions at the nature-insurance intersection operate in contexts where risk reduction benefits are diffused, upfront costs are high, and no single actor can bear them alone. Insurance rarely operates in isolation: for products to function, the underlying NbS project or natural asset typically needs a broader financial architecture that generates revenue(s), mobilises capital and sustains maintenance over time. Public-private partnerships are consistently identified as the most effective structure for making these products viable, though the roles played by public actors vary significantly.

Barrier identified in the guidance

Emerging solutions and suggested steps

Risk reduction benefits are diffused, making it hard for any single actor to bear the cost

EDF (2.2.3) and WWF (2.2.8) note that the protective benefits of ecosystems accrue to many stakeholders but implementation costs are too concentrated for any single actor to absorb. This is further amplified by the fact that most actors see risk reduction as a public good and view the public sector to be the main actor responsible for it (2.1.7, 2.1.8, 2.1.13).

- NATURANCE D4.3 (2.1.14) identifies public-private partnerships as the preferred mechanism, combining public risk-sharing with private sector underwriting expertise.
- Innovation Lab 4 (2.1.4), convened by CISL with the ClimateWise network, produced a phased roadmap for blended finance structures supported by 20 real-world examples, finding that grants are needed to initiate projects but that combining public, philanthropic and private capital is essential for long-term sustainability.

NbS projects often lack revenue streams from which premiums can be paid

NATURANCE D4.3 (2.1.14) and EDF (2.2.3) note that without mechanisms to monetise NbS benefits, there is often no financial flow from which premiums or performance-based incentives can be drawn.

- Mechanisms such as payments for ecosystem services, carbon or biodiversity credit revenues, and water-quality credits can create the cash flows to which insurance attaches.
- NATURANCE D4.3 (2.1.14) also notes that land acquisition costs represent a critical barrier, and that mixed-use arrangements combining agriculture with NbS could improve both financial feasibility and the ability to sustain premium payments over time.
- NATURANCE Innovation Lab (2.1.9), led by SU, further highlights that novel business models could emerge from NbS adoption to generate revenue, such as rearing water buffaloes in re-wetted land

Short-term insurance contract cycles misalign with long-term nature outcomes

Innovation Lab 7 (2.1.7) found that insurance engagement with conservation investments remains limited by contract cycles that do not match the multi-decade trajectory of ecosystem recovery.

- Howden and Pollination (2.2.5) and NATURANCE D3.3 (2.1.12) note that longer-term policy structures or rolling renewal commitments may be needed.
- Innovation Lab 9 (2.1.9) found that in Sweden, base funding is no longer the primary constraint; rather, landowners hesitate due to long-term risks including liability and technical failure, pointing to a role for tailored insurance in unblocking investment where the financing itself is already available.

Evidence from nature-related insurance products

The digital library confirms the importance of public-private partnerships, which account for 35% of all entries (Section 4.2). These take diverse forms: in the Belize Blue Bond (3.1.1), \$610 million in political risk insurance enabled a \$364 million conservation-linked debt restructuring; in Argentina (3.1.4), the provincial government purchases jaguar protection insurance and provides it free of charge to affected farmers. In San Crisanto (3.1.8), the mangrove community pays its parametric insurance premium from annual carbon credit sales, demonstrating how revenue-generating mechanisms can sustain premiums without ongoing subsidy. SCOR's restoration insurance (3.1.11) addresses the time-horizon barrier by structuring coverage and product offer across three ecosystem recovery stages. Fully public models remain rare, with only the NFIP Community Rating System (3.2.2) and the Illinois cover crop premium discount (3.2.3) identified.

Recommendations emerging from the guidance

- **Insurers** can actively seek participation in blended finance structures where **government** involvement de-risks the entry of private capital or subsidise premiums, rather than waiting for fully commercial conditions to emerge.
- **Policymakers and development finance institutions** can develop replicable partnership templates that clarify public and private roles, reducing transaction costs for future schemes.
- **NbS project developers and investors** would benefit from treating insurance as a de-risking layer that can unlock other forms of finance, and from engaging **insurers** early in project design to ensure products fit within the broader financing architecture.
- **Philanthropic funders and international organisations** are well placed to target early-stage premium financing and technical assistance to support products in moving from a pilot stage to commercial viability.

How can policy help create a market for nature-related insurance?

The literature identifies a clear relationship between regulatory frameworks and insurance product development at the nature-insurance intersection. Where policy mandates create obligations related to nature, such as restoration requirements or biodiversity offsets, demand for insurance products follows. Where these signals are absent, insurers face uncertain demand and unclear liability horizons that discourage engagement.

Barrier identified in the guidance

Emerging solutions and suggested steps

Absence of regulatory mandates means uncertain demand for nature-related products

Without clear obligations related to nature outcomes, insurers lack the demand signals needed to justify product development and underwriting commitment.

- Marsh McLennan ([2.2.15](#)) and NATURANCE D4.3 ([2.1.14](#)) point to the UK's Biodiversity Net Gain mandate as a transformative example, where a 30-year maintenance requirement for restored habitats has created clear demand for long-term insurance solutions covering liability and reversal risks.
- Innovation Lab 1 ([2.1.1](#)), convened by LSE with Flood Re, explored how BNG funding could be targeted at urban flood risk management.
- UNDP BIOFIN ([2.2.13](#)) highlights how Colombia's provision for non-agricultural parametric insurance opened regulatory space for product innovation.

Nature is still treated as a reputational concern rather than a financial governance priority

Without disclosure obligations, nature-related risks remain invisible in insurance portfolios and investment decisions.

- TNFD and UNEP FI ([2.2.11](#); [2.2.12](#)) note that mandatory disclosure frameworks are shifting nature towards a core financial governance priority, aligning with targets under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.
- UNEP FI's "Breaking Ground" ([2.2.12](#)) provides hands-on guidance for applying the TNFD's LEAP approach to insurance underwriting portfolios.

Evidence from nature-related insurance products

The digital library provides direct evidence of this relationship. Two digital library entries were products developed in response to nature-positive legislation: Marsh and AXA XL's biodiversity deductible reduction ([3.3.2](#)) followed France's 2016 biodiversity law, and the Illinois cover crop premium discount ([3.2.3](#)) was designed to advance the state's Nutrient Loss Reduction Strategy ([Section 4.1](#)). The SDG and GBF alignment analysis found that nearly 80% of products contribute to SDG 13, while GBF Targets 2 and 19 were among the most commonly addressed ([Section 4.3](#)), indicating alignment with international policy goals even where domestic regulation does not yet mandate it.

Recommendations emerging from the guidance

- **Policy makers** can develop regulatory anchors that link development permissions, land management obligations or financial disclosures to measurable nature outcomes, providing the long-term demand certainty that **insurers** need to justify product development.
- **Insurers** would benefit from engaging proactively with emerging regulatory frameworks such as BNG and TNFD rather than waiting for mandates to be finalised, positioning themselves to respond quickly as demand crystallises.
- **Regulators** can ensure that enabling legal frameworks explicitly accommodate nature-related insurance mechanisms, as demonstrated by Colombia's provision for non-agricultural parametric insurance.

How can improved data and modelling help insurers price nature-related risk?

Across the literature, the most frequently cited barrier at the nature-insurance intersection is the difficulty of quantifying the risk-reduction value of ecosystems in the terms that actuarial pricing requires. Traditional catastrophe models generally do not account for the presence or absence of natural barriers, which can lead to mispriced risk. Proof-of-concept modelling now exists across several hazard types, but these advances remain concentrated in a small number of well-resourced contexts.

Barrier identified in the guidance

Emerging solutions and suggested steps

Traditional catastrophe models do not account for natural barriers

Earth Security (2.2.14) and EDF (2.2.3) find that this leads to overpricing or false conclusions that assets in nature-rich areas are uninsurable.

- NATURANCE D4.2 (2.1.13) and D4.3 (2.1.14) develop improved object-level models that incorporate NbS as attenuation factors within flood risk assessments.
- Innovation Lab 2 (2.1.2), led by LSE, demonstrated that building-scale hydrological models can capture NbS impacts with the granularity needed for premium calculations.
- Innovation Lab 3 (2.1.3), led by IIASA, found that incorporating NbS into parametric wildfire insurance pricing could yield premium reductions of 20 to 43%.

High-resolution, spatially explicit data on ecosystem condition is lacking

Without localised data, insurers cannot calibrate products to reflect nature's risk-reduction value at the scales needed for underwriting.

- UNEP FI (2.2.11) and EDF (2.2.3) recommend partnerships between insurers, researchers and public data providers to generate spatially explicit datasets.
- Innovation Lab 5 (2.1.5), led by WTW, on urban heat in London identified the specific need for hyper-local temperature data to calibrate parametric products.
- Innovation Lab 9 (2.1.9), led by SU, on wetland restoration in Sweden concluded that monitoring infrastructure is a precondition for insurance products covering NbS performance.

Evidence from nature-related insurance products

The digital library shows that where modelling does capture the value of nature-based risk reduction, it translates into tangible pricing benefits: the California wildfire policy (3.2.1) achieved a 39% premium reduction on the basis of empirical analysis of ecological forest management. More broadly, parametric products account for a third of all entries in the digital library and are growing rapidly, with 75% established in the past three years (Section 4.2). Their use of predefined, transparent triggers tied to measurable environmental parameters offers a pathway for pricing nature-related risk where conventional indemnity-based loss assessment is harder to apply to ecosystem damage.

Recommendations emerging from the guidance

- **Insurers and catastrophe modelling firms** can integrate ecosystem condition as a variable within existing risk models, building on the proof-of-concept work demonstrated across wildfire, riverine flooding and coastal hazards.
- **Researchers, insurers and public data providers** can invest in spatial finance, remote sensing and monitoring infrastructure to generate the high-resolution data needed to price nature's protective value.
- **Policy makers** are well placed to support the development of transparent, open-access modelling platforms that enable systematic integration of NbS benefits into pricing and portfolio decisions across the broader market.

Annex B - Field Definitions

This annex provides definitions for all fields and field values used throughout the compendium. It is organised into two sections corresponding to the two main content types: Literature and Guidance, and Case Studies. For each section, an overview table describes every field that appears in the individual entries, followed by detailed definitions of the selectable values within key fields. These definitions ensure consistency across all entries and support accurate interpretation of the database.

B.1 Literature and Guidance – Overview of Fields

Field	Definition
Title	The official title of the publication or resource, as provided by the authoring organisation.
Description	A concise summary of the resource outlining its purpose, scope, stakeholders involved, key findings, and primary outputs.
Publication Year	The year in which the resource was first published or officially released.
Type of Resource	The format and intent of the publication, reflecting how it is designed to be used. The full set of resource types are defined in the Field Values section below.
Regional Coverage	The geographic scope to which the resource primarily applies or from which its evidence is drawn.
Knowledge Level	The level of prior knowledge assumed of the reader. The full set of knowledge levels are defined in the Field Values section below.
Target Audience	The primary stakeholder group(s) for whom the resource is intended. The full set of target audiences are defined in the Field Values section below.

Partners	Organisations that formally contributed to the development, funding, or publication of the resource.
Sources	Primary access point to the resource.

B.2 Literature and Guidance – Field Values and Definitions

Type of Resource	Definition
Policy Report	Publication aimed at informing or influencing policy or regulatory decisions. Typically synthesises evidence and provides recommendations for governments or international organisations.
Working Paper	Preliminary or exploratory publication presenting early findings or concepts for discussion and feedback. Often not peer-reviewed.
Academic Research	Scholarly publication presenting original research or analysis, usually peer-reviewed, intended for expert or academic audiences.
Implementation Guide	Practical resource providing step-by-step guidance, tools, or methods to implement policies, projects, or tools.
Corporate Publication	Publication by a private-sector organisation showcasing strategies, products, case studies, or commitments, often for internal or external audiences.

Target Audience	Definition
Public Sector (Government & Policymakers)	Government agencies, regulators, or policymakers.
Private Sector	Businesses, industry groups, or corporate stakeholders.
Civil Society	NGOs, community organisations, and advocacy groups.
International Organisations	Multilateral or intergovernmental organisations (e.g. UN, World Bank).

Donors & Philanthropy	Foundations, philanthropic institutions, and development funders.
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Knowledge Level	Definition
Beginner	Introductory content; minimal prior knowledge required.
Intermediate	Some prior familiarity assumed; includes applied analysis or examples.
Expert	Advanced or technical content; intended for specialists or researchers.

The following section defines the fields and field values used in the case study entries. While several fields, such as Title, Description, Partners, and Sources, are shared with the Literature and Guidance section, the case study entries include additional fields specific to insurance product design, risk classification, and project implementation. Where a field shares the same name across both sections, its definition has been tailored to reflect the context in which it is used.

B.3 Case Studies – Overview of Fields

Field	Definition
Title	The official or commonly used name of the insurance product, solution, or case study.
Description	A concise overview of the insurance solution or case, explaining its purpose, structure, how it functions, and key results or outcomes.
Start / End Year	The year in which the insurance product, pilot, or project has (or will) begin and end.
Project Maturity	The stage of development or implementation of the insurance solution (e.g. Concept phase, design phase, pilot phase, active).
Country / Region	The countries or global regions where the insurance product is in operation/available.

Realm	The broad environmental domain (terrestrial, freshwater, marine or subterranean) in which the project operates, as defined by the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology.
Insurance Provider / Scheme Developers	The type of institution(s) providing insurance, guarantees, or investment capital. The full set of scheme developers are defined in the Field Values section below.
Insurance Trigger Type	The mechanism by which an insurance payout or financial response is activated. The full set of trigger types are defined in the Field Values section below.
Insured Risk	The type of risk or exposure being transferred or managed by the insurance product. A single product may address more than one type of insurable risk. The full set of insured risks are defined in the Field Values section below.
Broader Risk	The kind of broader societal risk that an insurance product addresses (adapted from TNFD framework of risk). For further details please see Annex C.
UNEP FI Category	Categorises product into one of UNEP FI’s 3 kinds of insurance: insurance for nature-positive, resilience insurance and transition insurance (see section 3 for further details).
NATURANCE Framework	Categorises product based on directionality of relationship between insurance product and nature: ‘insurance for nature’ or ‘nature for insurance’. For further details please see Annex C.
Insurance Scheme Target	The beneficiary of the insurance scheme. The full set of scheme targets are defined in the Field Values section below.
Insurance Product Type	The role that the insurance product plays in relation to nature, reflecting its purpose and design function, adapted from UNEP FI. A product may be tagged with more than one type. See section 3 for further details.
Partners	Key organisations involved in designing, funding, implementing, or underwriting the insurance solution.
Sources	Primary public sources describing the case study.
Database Origin	The organisation or entity that submitted or contributed the case study.

B.4 Case Studies – Field Values and Definitions

Project Maturity	Definition
Concept Phase	Early idea or design; not yet formally developed or funded.
Design Phase	Structured product design in progress or completed.
Pilot Phase	Tested at a limited scale to assess feasibility or performance.
Active	Fully implemented and operational.
Completed	Concluded; no longer active, with outcomes ideally realised or evaluated.

Insurance Trigger Type	Definition
Parametric/Index	Payout triggered by a predefined parameter or index, without loss assessment.
Indemnity	Payout based on verified losses or damages incurred.
Unknown	Trigger mechanism is not sufficiently specified.

Insurance Provider / Scheme Developers	Definition
Private	Commercial insurers, reinsurers, investors, banks, or asset managers.
Public	Governments, state-owned entities, DFIs, or multilateral institutions.

Public-Private-Partnership	Formal risk-sharing or co-financing between public and private actors.
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Insured Risk	Definition
Physical Risk to People, Assets, and Economic Activity	Risk that physical hazards lead to loss of life, damage to property and infrastructure, or disruption to businesses, communities, and supply chains.
Risk to Natural Assets and Ecosystems	Risk that physical hazards lead to loss or degradation of ecosystems, species, or natural assets.
Political and Sovereign Credit Risk	Risk that public (or private) obligors fail to meet financial commitments related to nature-positive activities due to political, regulatory, or credit-related factors, regardless of physical outcomes.
Liability and Policy Risk	Risk of financial loss arising from new, changing, or enforced policies, regulations, or legal claims related to nature impacts or nature-positive obligations.
Performance and Delivery Risk	Risk that a nature-positive activity, project, or asset fails to deliver intended outcomes or benefits, even in the absence of a discrete physical hazard. <i>(Applies to NbS projects, carbon or biodiversity credits, and outcome-based finance.)</i>

Insurance Scheme Target	Definition
Local Communities	Community-level beneficiaries including fisherfolk, farmers, and coastal populations.
Public Sector	Government agencies, public bodies, and sovereign entities.
Private – Investors	Private-sector investors, financiers, and asset holders.
Private – Real Economy	Private-sector entities operating in the real economy, such as manufacturers, agricultural producers, and service providers.
Philanthropies	Philanthropic foundations, conservation NGOs, and other non-profit entities that fund, deliver, or benefit from the insurance scheme.

Land Managers	Entities responsible for the stewardship, management, or restoration of natural ecosystems, such as protected area authorities or conservation trusts.
Unknown	Insurance scheme target not specified or not yet determined.

Annex C - Nature Insurance Risk Framework

The landscape of nature-based insurance solutions terminology is complex and fast developing, with a need for a clear framework defining types of nature-based insurance solutions, who they are targeted at and how they interact with nature. Organisations and initiatives, including NATURANCE, UNEP FI and WWF, are creating movement in this space, developing terminology and framings that are both progressive in creating a shared understanding and market-aligned. This Annex includes an overview of the NATURANCE terms used within the compendium, including defining a broader risk-based framework that is complementary to existing frameworks in the market.

The nature insurance risk framework connects nature-related insurance products with the intended risk outcomes of the insurance solution, i.e. the broader risk the solution addresses. Broader risks can be defined as the effects on ecosystems, economies and communities that the product, taken as a whole contributes to addressing. This framework builds on TNFD's definitions of nature-related physical and transition risks to identify 3 types of risk that can be addressed by insurance solutions. Table C.1 below contains definitions for these terms.

Broader Risk-based framework

Insurance addressing Risks to Nature

Insurance solutions designed directly to address risks to the condition and extent of ecosystems and species population size and extinction risk. These include physical damage from hazards, degradation from human activity, and barriers to effective conservation, restoration and NbS implementation

Examples range from parametric coral reef insurance that funds post-storm restoration to indemnity products that compensate farmers for livestock losses from wildlife, reducing incentives to harm wildlife or enhance recovery of natural assets.

Insurance for Nature-related Transition Risk to People, Business and the Economy

Insurance solutions designed to address risks arising from shifts in policy, regulation, technology, markets and public sentiment as economies move towards nature-positive

outcomes. These include increased compliance costs, loss of market access and reputational damage from nature-negative activities

For example, insurance to cover the performance/delivery risks of nature or carbon credits utilised by businesses as part of their nature management strategies.

Insurance addressing Nature-related Physical Risk to People, Business and the Economy

Insurance solutions designed address risks arising from changes in ecosystems that alter the services on which people, businesses and economies depend. These include disruption to operations and supply chains, loss of natural protection against hazards and increased costs of degraded natural inputs.

For example, by channeling a part of premiums to restoring mangroves, the Green Life Programme in El Salvador reverses the loss in mangroves which subsequently reduces local communities' exposure to storm damages (UNDRR, 2025)

Table C.1: Definitions of Broader Nature-related Risk Addressed

The broader risk addressed by the insurance product is not necessarily the same as the risk that is directly insured by the product. For example, the Hiscox insurance for decommissioning end of life offshore assets provide liability coverage for the decommissioning and removal of offshore assets. In this case, the risk directly being insured is liability risk, yet the broader risk being addressed by the scheme is the risk to nature, by remediating negative impacts on nature which have impacted the condition of ecosystems. Figure C.1 outlines the different types of directly insurable risks and relates them to the broader nature-related risks.

Types of Risk Addressed by Nature-related Insurance Products

Figure C.1: Risks addressed by nature-related insurance products

The directly insured risk characterises the specific exposure being priced and underwritten, concerned with the probability and severity of a defined loss event against which a premium can be charged. Broader nature-related risks, by contrast, reflect a systems-wide perspective, capturing the second- and third-order effects on a wider set of stakeholders, economies and ecosystems that flow from the insurance intervention. These do not map one-to-one: a single product may address multiple broader risks, and a single broader risk may correspond to several different insured risk types.

Insurable risks and broader nature-related risks are not unrelated; the former traces to the latter through the design and context of each product. The same insurable risk type can relate to different broader risks depending on what the product is designed to achieve and the setting in which it operates. Refer to [Section 4.5](#) for examples.

‘Insurance for Nature’ and ‘Nature for Insurance’ definitions

The ‘Insurance for Nature’ and ‘Nature for Insurance’ dichotomy has underpinned much of the NATURANCE project. This distinction has provided an important framing to highlight the complex interaction between nature and insurance. Table C.2 below contains definitions for these terms.

'Insurance for Nature' and 'Nature for Insurance': Definitions

Insurance for nature

Insurance solutions that play a role in conserving, protecting or restoring nature, or avoiding or mitigating drivers of nature change, addressing risks to nature. For example insurance for marine protected areas (MPAs) in the Philippines use parametric triggers to disburse funds for debris removal, coral restoration and MPA infrastructure repairs thereby catalysing the recovery of insured natural assets (i.e., corals) and systems protecting nature (i.e., MPAs and their infrastructure). In this case, the insurance addresses cyclones which form a risk to nature (Jimenez-Sanchez, 2024).

Relating back to the broader nature-related risk framing, the 'Insurance for Nature' categorisation is interconnected with insurance products that address risks to nature.

Nature for insurance

Insurance solutions where nature-based risk-reduction forms part of the strategy to address a risk to built assets, communities or portfolios. To elucidate as part of the Community Rating System, natural flood management techniques are allocated points that count towards premium discounts. This encourages property owners/municipalities to use nature-based approaches to reduce their vulnerability and exposure to floods (FEMA, 2025).

Relating back to the broader nature-related risk framing, the 'Nature for Insurance' categorisation is interconnected with insurance products that address nature-related physical risks to people, business and the economy.

Table C.2: Definitions of NATURANCE Nature-based Insurance

There also exist insurance products which address nature-related physical and transition risks to people, business and the economy but do not have a direct impact on nature. For example, standard contents cover against flood risk in the UK for example, purely covers contents of tenants or owner-occupiers in their homes, addressing a physical risk, but does not insure any form of NbS nor does it typically include underwriting provisions that are nature positive (Flood Re, 2025).